

PLAN'EAT

Toolbox for Behavior Change Intervention Strategies

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T4.3: Micro-level: Interventions, strategies and tools targeting consumers

T4.3.1. Toolbox for intervention strategies to promote behaviour change

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DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

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Executive summary

This toolbox is an output of the PLAN'EAT project, aimed at transforming food systems to promote healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours. The project employs a multi-actor, three-tiered approach: macro-level (food systems), meso-level (food environments), and micro-level (individual consumers). This document focuses on micro-level strategies, providing scientifically validated methodologies for designing, implementing, and evaluating behaviour change interventions targeting diverse consumer groups. The toolbox will present methods and strategies for policy makers to design interventions to promote consumer food behaviour change.

The toolbox serves dual purposes: guiding policymakers and researchers in planning evidence-based interventions and supporting subsequent PLAN'EAT tasks. Its methodologies prioritize collaboration, contextual relevance, and adaptability, aiming to foster healthier, more sustainable consumer choices while addressing systemic barriers and enablers.

Central to this effort are the PLANEAT project's nine living labs across Europe, representing varied demographic groups and settings. These labs serve as testing grounds for interventions tailored to specific contexts, behaviours, and epidemiological needs. Leveraging frameworks such as the Behaviour Change Wheel and COM-B model, the toolbox outlines pathways to identify leverage points, develop interventions,

and evaluate outcomes. It builds on a robust evidence base, synthesizing insights from systematic reviews, stakeholder consultations, and participatory research.

Introduction

Poor dietary habits significantly contribute to the global health crisis, fuelling the prevalence of obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and other nutrition-related health issues. Furthermore, the production and consumption of food has a great impact on the environment. Diets high in animal-based products, such as meat and dairy, contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, and water scarcity due to the resource-intensive nature of livestock farming. Conversely, plant-based diets generally have a lower environmental footprint, requiring fewer natural resources and generating less pollution. Food waste further exacerbates environmental issues, as discarded food contributes to methane emissions in landfills and represents wasted water, energy, and labour. Shifting toward sustainable dietary patterns can mitigate environmental harm while promoting global food security.

Tackling these challenges goes beyond individual efforts and necessitates systemic approaches that promote environments conducive to healthier and more sustainable eating. Policy measures such as taxing certain types of unhealthy and unsustainable foods, subsidizing alternatives, implementing trustworthy labelling, and running education campaigns in school settings are instrumental in helping shaping consumer food choices.

Policy strategies are vital because they address the broader social, economic, and environmental factors that influence dietary decisions. Individual food choices are rarely made in isolation, as they are shaped by a combination of factors, including food availability, affordability, cultural values, and marketing tactics. In the absence of effective policy measures, these factors often encourage unhealthy eating habits, making it difficult for individuals to adopt healthier diets. By modifying the food landscape and aligning economic and social incentives with healthier options, policy-driven interventions can achieve long-lasting, widespread improvements in dietary behaviours.

The PLAN'EAT project aims at implementing a multi-actor approach at three levels; macro (food system), meso (food environment) and micro (individual consumer). As an output of task 4.3.1 of the PLANEAT project, this toolbox will present methods and strategies for designing interventions led by policy makers, researchers, and other types of decisions makers, to promote behaviour change at *micro* level, i.e. targeting consumers. By combining policy strategies and interventions, the toolbox consists of recommendations to develop, test and validate interventions tailored for behaviours, contexts, and target groups specific to the populations of the nine living labs of the PLAN'EAT project, rather than the broader population.

This toolbox presents recommendations resulting from the research and work performed during the PLAN'EAT project by project partners. The content of the toolbox builds on and combines the PLAN'EAT project's previous findings, such as mappings of existing intervention strategies, and methods for identifying high impact behaviours and key leverage points. Targeting policymakers and researchers to build their future activities on a solid scientific basis, the toolbox has been reviewed and validated by the PLAN'EAT Policy Lab represented by EPHA.

The main aim of the toolbox is to serve as a scientific basis for EU policymakers and researchers to plan, design, and evaluate their future activities and interventions on. Further objectives of the toolbox are to, a) form the base of the PLAN'EAT task 4.3.2, in which JLU and EUFIC will design one behavioural change intervention per living lab target group (except the two clinical settings in Germany and Italy), and b) serve as a guide in the PLAN'EAT task 4.3.3 in which TUM and UNIBO will design effective behavioural change interventions as part of their clinical studies in the German and Italian living labs, targeting children/adolescents and adults with diabetes/obesity, respectively.

The outline

The applied methodology of the toolbox on how to design, carry out and evaluate behaviour change intervention strategies are inspired by The BehaviourWorks Method Book (Bragge et al., 2021), which describes different behaviour change skills and approaches for use in partnership with government and industry across a range of contexts, and the OECD Regulatory Policy Outlook (2021), Chapter II, on evidence-based policy making and stakeholder engagement, which critically examines recent trends and progress made by OECD member countries and the European Union in attaining agreed OECD recommendations.

Figure 1. The BehaviourWorks Method (Bragge et al., 2021)

More specifically, the methodology follows below sequence and areas, which will be presented in the following chapters:

The nine PLAN'EAT living labs

The European Network of Living Labs defines living labs as: “(...) open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments based on a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation activities in communities and/or multi-stakeholder environments, placing citizens and/or end-users at the centre of the innovation process.” To apply this participatory and multi-actor approach, PLAN'EAT is implementing most of its activities in nine living labs, each targeting a specific population group, by creating a citizen panel of 60-200 consumers (see Table 1). The population groups have been selected for their potential for behavioural change, low representativeness in existing studies and statistics, ability to influence other population groups, foreseen impact of interventions, and epidemiological needs. The vulnerability of the study subjects and gender have also been considered.

Table 1 : PLAN'EAT Living Labs		
Living lab	Target group	Setting
France (Auvergne)	Healthy children and adolescents, middle and high socioeconomic status (SES), urban, peri-urban and rural (6-15 years)	School and LL citizen community
Germany (Bavaria)	Obese and overweight children and adolescents from a cohort in Germany (10-18 years)	Clinical
Greece (Attica)	Elderly people, NCDs, all SES (> 60 years)	Free-living population
Hungary (Budapest)	Healthy young adults, low SES (single parents) (20 – 30 years)	Citizen community
Ireland (Dublin)	Healthy young adults – University students, all SES (18-30 years)	University Campus
Italy (Bologna – Pilastro)	Diabetic adults from low SES (low income/ rural/ immigrants), (18-70 years).	Clinical
Poland (Kracow)	Healthy children and adolescents, low SES (1-16 years)	School, kindergarten, and household
Spain (Catalonia)	Healthy adults from middle age to elderly, all SES, (40-85 years)	Citizen community
Sweden	Healthy toddlers, middle and high SES (<6 years)	Pre-school and household

Figure 2 below provides a visual overview of the nine PLAN'EAT target groups of the living labs by age group and selected characteristic such as socioeconomic status (SES) or the presence of a non-communicable

disease (NCD).

Figure 2: Target groups of the PLAN'EAT living labs

1. Identifying the problem

1. Understand the system and learn from stakeholders

To describe the concepts and methods that the PLAN'EAT project has applied to understand the status of the food system, and to present the findings from the nine living lab countries, this section will summarize the work and findings of Erik Mathijs and Francesca Vespa, KUL, as part of the PLAN'EAT deliverable 2.2.

While targeting and focusing on consumer behavior, it is important to bear in mind that this cannot be done without looking at the surroundings and conditions in which it is taking place. Promoting healthy and sustainable diets requires more than just educating consumers, as their choices are shaped by the food environments in which they make decisions. It is increasingly recognised that dietary behaviour is influenced by the environments in which people live, learn, work and play (Moran et al., 2020). Food environments can be divided into the "community environment," which encompasses the food sources accessible within a community, and the "consumer environment," which pertains to the variety, presentation, and pricing of products at each source (Glanz et al., 2005; Caspi et al., 2012). Evidence suggests that the consumer environment significantly shapes dietary behaviors, making food stores a point for influencing food choices and implementing dietary interventions (Middel et al., 2019). Consequently, public health strategies and interventions can target these environments.

The conceptual model defined by Turner et al. (2018) describes the food environment as "the interface that mediates people's food acquisition and consumption within the wider food system. It encompasses external dimensions such as the availability, prices, vendor and product properties, and promotional information; and personal dimensions such as the accessibility, affordability, convenience and desirability of food sources and products". Emphasis is put on food environments resulting from the interaction between external (e.g. marketing, retail and product properties, prices, and availability), and personal domains (e.g. convenience, acceptability, affordability), as being part of wider food systems (as depicted in Figure 3).

Figure 3. Conceptual model of the food environment (Turner et al, 2018)

PLAN'EAT CASE STUDY

EXPLORATIVE STUDY OF EUROPEAN FOOD CHAIN ACTORS

To evaluate the **determinants of the implementation of interventions** aimed to promote healthy dietary behaviours in food environments, an explorative study with members of five collaborative working groups (CWG) representing the European food chain actors (farmers, food industries, retailers, food services and restaurants), was carried out as part of the PLANEAT project to:

- Assess the **knowledge and awareness** of the CWG members about healthy and sustainable food;
- Explore the **determinants** that CWG members perceive as **facilitating and/or inhibiting to the implementation of interventions** in their food environment.

The study aimed to evaluate the factors perceived by CWG members as hindering or facilitating the success of an intervention aimed at promoting healthier or more sustainable dietary behaviour.

The study consisted of three parts:

- A **study of the literature** about the determinants experienced by retailers, owners and interventionists in the implementation of healthy food store interventions conducted to generate a long list of barriers and enablers.
- From the long list of barriers and enablers, the CWG leaders selected and compiled a **short list of key determinants** that best represented the characteristics of the food environments in which the CWG members operate.
- From these shortlists, CWG members were asked to indicate which of the determinants proposed are **perceived as barriers or enablers** in implementing interventions to make their food environments healthier and more sustainable.

Results from the literature

The first part of the study was to gain an understanding of interventions already tested and evaluated in literature, aimed at encouraging healthier eating behaviours through changes in the food environment, such as changes in pricing, availability, promotion or advertising of healthy and sustainable foods. The systematic

review of Middel et al. (2019) was used as a reference to collect a list of the healthy food store interventions (HFI) implemented in food stores published in 41 original studies. The determinants defined as 'barriers' had a negative impact on the implementation or on outcomes of the intervention; while those defined as 'enablers' had a positive impact on the implementation or outcomes of the intervention. Barriers and enablers were categorized according to domains of origins and themes. The list of determinants provided by the systematic review conducted by Middel et al. is available in Annex A.

Adaptation to the food actor context

In order to adapt the results of Middel et al. to the different consumer environments in which the CWG members operate by producing, processing and supplying food, KUL carried out one-on-one consultations with the CWG leaders. During the consultations, the long list of determinants that can influence the success or failure of HFIs in the food stores identified by Middel et al., was presented to the CWG leaders, who were then asked to identify the determinants that their members (farmers, food industries, retailers, food services and restaurants) may have experienced when implementing interventions aimed at promoting healthier and more sustainable food choices through the adoption of HFIs or, in the case of farmers, sustainable farming practices. Following the consultations, each CWG leader selected the determinants that best fitted the context of their members and compiled a short list of determinants from the long list by Middel et al.

Open-ended survey

CWG leaders were asked to conduct an open-ended survey to validate the determinants (barriers and enablers) in the short list they had selected to conduct an open-ended survey with their members.

The objectives of the open-ended survey were:

- 1) to assess CWG members' **knowledge and awareness** of healthy and sustainable food.
- 2) to understand whether the **determinants** selected by CWG leaders had been trialed by members in implementing actions to make their consumer environments healthier and more sustainable.
- 3) to know whether CWG members experienced the proposed determinants as a **barrier or enabler** in the implementation of the interventions.

CWG leaders were surveyed in two ways: individual interviews (online surveys) or group discussions (webinars/workshops). A facilitation guide for conducting the open-ended survey is provided in Annex B. The total number of participants involved the study were 98: 8 from restaurants, 4 retailers, 17 farmers, 18 from food service, and 51 from food industries.

Findings

The conclusions reported below provide a summary of the most relevant results of the study. For a detailed overview of the findings, please refer to Annex C.

The question on the definition of healthy and sustainable food was put to the CWGs in order to check their level of knowledge on healthy and sustainable foods/meals and to verify if there is a homogeneity of answers among the different actors in the food chain. The responses from the various CWGs were fairly uniform: a healthy food product provides the right amount of nutrients needed for a healthy and balanced diet, which has a positive impact on physical and mental health. Healthy food is also sustainable and vice versa, as the two concepts are often linked. A food can be defined as sustainable if the natural, human, and animal resources needed to produce it are reduced to a minimum. For most respondents, a healthy and sustainable product is unprocessed, locally produced and seasonal.

To characterize the barriers that stakeholders may encounter when implementing interventions aimed at providing or producing healthy and sustainable food, **three main domains** emerged as relevant to all CWG members: **outer setting, inner setting, and intervention**. In particular, the determinants that CWG members perceived as barriers to the implementation of HFIs were related to:

- 1) the **characteristics of consumers**, their low demand for healthier and more sustainable products, the lack of consumer knowledge about the benefits of these products,
- 2) the **lack of clear European and national guidelines** to support this type of intervention, and
- 3) the **structural and supply deficiencies** of healthy and sustainable food. CWG members indicated that they need more support from experts for training in the management of healthy and sustainable products and for promoting healthy and sustainable food in a way that will be more attractive to consumers.

For CWG members, the consumer's adherence to traditional cuisine and scepticism towards healthy and sustainable food due to its lower sensory appeal are significant factors that negatively impact their decision to implement HFIs. Additionally, CWGs have identified the need to support higher costs associated with purchasing (for restaurants, retailers, and food services) and producing (for the food industry and farmers) healthy and sustainable products. According to CWG members, actions promoted and funded by European and national policies lack common objectives, as European policies are not well-aligned with national guidelines. An analysis of the enablers identified by the CWG members reveals that most belong to the external setting rather than the internal setting. This indicates that respondents are primarily seeking incentives or subsidies from national or EU institutions. They prefer interventions that are straightforward to implement and do not necessitate significant running costs or the acquisition of new skills and machinery. During the implementation process, CWGs recommended encouraging both intra- and inter-cooperation. Furthermore, fostering a robust community relationship with food actors, particularly farmers, can motivate them to successfully execute the specific HFIs intervention. Many of the enablers proposed by the CWG members underscore the necessity of food education campaigns aimed at consumers, who need to adapt to national culinary traditions.

1.2 Review evidence and current policy efforts

1.2.1 Research evidence

Reviewing existing research enables a comprehensive understanding of the issue at hand, examines strategies employed by others globally, and supports evidence-based decision-making. The insights derived from a body of research can substantially enhance problem-solving efforts by illuminating effective solutions and pinpointing areas where resources might be inefficiently used on unsuccessful approaches. This chapter elucidates how research reviews consolidate this knowledge, rendering it accessible and actionable for policymakers and leaders addressing complex challenges.

To start the review process, the following questions can be asked:

- Which behaviour change strategies change food consumption towards healthy and/or sustainable choices?
- What does the combined systematic evidence from all systematic reviews indicate about behaviour change potential/behavioural plasticity?
- What types or groups of behaviour change strategies are successful?
- In which contexts and for whom are these successful?
 - What are inter-individual/inter-group differences (e.g., socio-demographics like gender and age)
 - What are differences between settings (e.g., home or school)?
 - What are further relevant intervention characteristics that are related to intervention success (e.g., intervention length or mode of delivery)?
- What challenges and gaps for identifying successful behaviour change strategies exist in the review-level literature, and related to that at the overview of reviews level?

In their internal report (IR1), JLU summarised behavioural scientific evidence for the potential of changing dietary-related behaviours through behaviour change interventions.

Applying above research questions, a review of the literature regarding behaviour change of food choice behaviours was performed. The result can be found in Annex D, which presents tables with a selection of research evidence for behaviour change techniques (BCTs) tested with the nine target groups of the PLANEAT project. Annex D serves as an overview of which strategies have been tested, and as a compilation of literature to look for further information regarding these strategies. It is important to note that the tables can only be a first guiding step in which strategies to choose. Once a few possible strategies are selected, it is essential to check the original studies behind them and understand in detail in which contexts the strategies have been applied and tested, including such aspects as the setting, duration, delivery type and further specifics of the target group.

The results indicate that while not all interventions and strategies are equally effective, there is evidence that some behaviour change interventions can modify dietary-related behaviours. Questions remain regarding the persistence of effects, as not all interventions measure long-term outcomes at extended follow-up intervals. Additionally, due to the wide variety of outcome variables and their combinations in the research, it is unclear whether it is more effective to target a specific outcome such as fruit and vegetable consumption, or to design interventions from a lifestyle perspective that target multiple behaviours within and across different domains (e.g., including physical activity behaviours).

1.2.2. Analytical framework for food policy interventions

As part of the work on deliverable 1.1 of the PLAN'EAT project, CREA and partners created a framework useful for analysing existing food policy interventions regarding healthy and sustainable food consumption in the 11 project countries. The focus was on:

- a) the extent to which governments have adopted explicit food policies;
- b) what goals they focus on;
- c) what instruments and calibrations they specifically use and apply.

CONCEPTUALIZING FOOD POLICY EFFORTS

The promotion of healthy and sustainable food consumption, and with it the prevention of diet-related diseases and negative environmental impacts, is not only of individual but also of societal relevance. It hence should not only focus on individuals, but on the wide range of actors that can have an influence on food choices. This chapter summarizes a selection of relevant policy reports offering this wider perspective, allowing insights into behaviour change topics and intervention strategies that are relevant at policy level, as well as some selected practice examples that are already implemented.

To get a better understanding of existing policy interventions on food consumption in the 11 EU member states represented in the project, three levels of analysis were distinguished: food policy domains, food policy indicators and food policy instruments.

Food policy domains

The food policy domains are adapted from the INFORMAS Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI), which was created in 2014 to monitor and support government actions on food environments. Of the 56 countries using Food-EPIs, over twenty have finalized their reports, including Poland, the Netherlands, Ireland, and Germany. In France, Belgium, and Spain, the process is still ongoing. While Food-EPI focuses on health, the PLANEAT project also considers sustainability, requiring some modifications to the index.

Food policy domains can be defined as “components of the political system and/or settings organized around substantive [food-related] issues [that] differ the target health goal/behaviour i.e. food or physical activity” (Harrington, 2020, p.12). The following food policy domains can be distinguished:

- Food prices: refers to food pricing, with measures like taxes and subsidies to promote healthy and/or sustainable food and limit unhealthy and unsustainable food choices.
- Food retail: refers to the power of governments “to implement policies and programmes to support the availability of healthy foods and limit the availability of unhealthy foods in communities (outlet density and locations) and in-store (product placement)” (Harrington, 2020, p.19).

- Food provision: refers to healthy and/or sustainable food service policies in settings funded by government (such as schools and other public sector settings) and encouragement of private sector to promote healthy and/or sustainable food choices.
- Food promotion/advertising: refers to policies to reduce the impact (exposure and power) of promoting unhealthy and/or unsustainable foods to children across all media and in places where children gather. For our purposes, we have also added a specific indicator on meat promotion, for all ages.
- Food labelling: refers to “consumer-orientated labelling on food packaging and menu boards in restaurants to enable consumers to easily make informed food choices and to prevent misleading claims” (Harrington, 2020, p.12).
- Food composition: refers to government systems that ensure that processed foods should minimise energy density and so-called ‘nutrients of concern’ (salt, (saturated, trans) fat, added sugar) (Harrington, 2020).

Food policy indicators

A subset of food policy indicators is used to show specific policy efforts within a food policy domain. Based on the INFORMAS Food-EPI with some modifications, it measures food composition by the presence of population intake targets or standards for unhealthy or unsustainable foods (e.g., salt, fats, sugar) and whether monitoring systems exist to track these targets or standards.

Example of policy indicators include:

- zoning laws and policies are robust enough for (local) governments to ensure that there is a ready availability of outlets selling fresh fruit and vegetables;
- zoning laws and policies are robust enough for local governments to place limits on the density or placement of quick-serve restaurants or other outlets selling mainly unhealthy and/or unsustainable foods in communities;
- there are existing support systems to encourage food stores to promote the in-store availability of healthy and/or sustainable foods, and to limit the in-store availability of unhealthy and/or unsustainable foods.

Food policy instruments

Additionally, a further categorization of more specific types of policy instruments related to food within a policy indicator is undertaken. Policy instruments are mechanisms of governmental intervention that may vary in their calibration, such as in particular numbers, targets, or timelines they propose, as well as in their degree of coercion, indicating the extent to which an instrument is mandatory.

PLAN'EAT CASE STUDY

POLICY INDICATORS OF THE 11 PLAN'EAT COUNTRIES

A policy framework study examined existing policy indicators and instruments for healthy and sustainable food consumption in the 11 European PLANEAT project countries (Belgium, Netherlands, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Spain, and Sweden). It found that **sustainable food consumption policies are underdeveloped**, with sustainability scoring only 6/25 compared to 18/25 for health. **Countries vary significantly in their policy indicators**. Belgium, the Netherlands, and Germany scored highest on health (18/25), while Greece scored lowest (8/25). The study also noted **differences in the degree of coercion in policies**; France uses more regulatory measures, while the Netherlands prefers exhortative and expenditure instruments. Belgium, the Netherlands, and France showed similar policy instruments across domains.

In general, **strategies for promoting healthy and sustainable food consumption remain cautious and often lack mandatory measures**. The study emphasizes the need for the European Union to enhance its food policies, with local governments playing a key role, particularly in implementing zoning regulations to restrict unhealthy and unsustainable food outlets. Policies designed to improve health, such as encouraging the

consumption of unprocessed and plant-based foods, could also support sustainability objectives. However, the study cautions that the data may not fully capture the actual policy landscape in each country.

1.2.3. Food policy strategies

The promotion of healthy and sustainable food consumption, along with the prevention of diet-related diseases and environmental impacts, is important for both individuals and society. Thus, the focus should extend beyond individuals to encompass the diverse range of actors that can shape food choices. This chapter provides an overview of relevant policy efforts from this broader perspective, offering insights into behaviour change topics and intervention strategies at the policy level, as well as some selected practice examples already in place. A list with links to the respective policy reports (numbers in brackets) can be found at the end of the chapter.

The NOURISHING framework

Building and sustaining healthy and sustainable food environments lies equally in the responsibility of consumers as well as all other relevant actors, such as policy makers, food producers or food retailers. This can be achieved e.g., by making the healthy and sustainable choice the easiest choice (3), by implementing nutrition label standards, healthy food standards in public institutions, economic tools to address affordability, restrictions for commercial promotion of unhealthy foods or product reformulations (11)

Besides changes in the food environment, the WCRF International's NOURISHING framework (11) defines two further key domains for policy:

- the food system, e.g., working with food suppliers to provide healthier ingredients and creating governance structures for stakeholder engagement; and
- behaviour change communication, e.g., raising public awareness, providing nutritional information and skills in school curricula or nutrition counselling) (8).

Since consumption decisions are influenced by various factors beyond available information, awareness campaigns and fact-based education alone may be insufficient to induce behavioural change. A well-designed combination of different tools across all domains is necessary to enable consumers to make informed choices, including behavioural tools such as default options or labels on packaging (3). Additionally, it is important to develop policies that address potential unequal effects due to income and other socioeconomic factors. One specific goal should be to reach all age groups, with an emphasis on children, to help them start life with better overall health (2, 5).

The following sections detail strategies from the two NOURISHING policy domains of *food environments* and *behaviour change communication*. The third domain, *food systems*, is not covered here but remains equally important. The focus is on the other two domains because they more directly influence consumer decision-making.

Education and intervention in the school environment

Policy considerations regarding children and adolescents should encompass the implementation of mandatory national food standards for childcare settings, recreational facilities, and schools, as well as providing free meals in these environments. To ensure equitable access to healthy food for all children, such programs should particularly target early school years and children from low-income households. Research from the United Kingdom indicates that food prepared in schools is healthier than food brought from home (5). Government provision of free school meals has been demonstrated to improve children's intake of healthy foods and lead to modest reductions in unhealthy body weight. For instance, the Greek DIATROFI programme effectively reduced food insecurity and childhood obesity by combining healthy school meals with an educational component on nutrition. Similarly, in Spain, an EU co-funded school programme promotes healthy eating habits among children through the provision of fruits, vegetables, and milk in schools, alongside an increase in VAT on sugar-sweetened beverages and drinks with added sweeteners (5).

Furthermore, incorporating statutory nutrition education into educational curricula could be beneficial, including practical skills such as cooking classes and age-appropriate framing. For adolescents, framing healthy eating as a strategy for addressing the climate crisis may be an effective approach (5). Previous research also indicates that reframing healthy eating as a means of resisting manipulative food marketing strategies led to improved dietary choices in school cafeterias for at least three months (5).

Studies have shown that combining interventions is more effective than educational input alone. A combination of education and positive feedback via smartphones has had a positive effect on fruit and vegetable consumption among students. Additionally, positive changes in behaviour were more likely when educational information was supplemented with activities outside the classroom, such as school gardening or cooking. An evaluation of educational tools suggests that fact-based teaching about sustainability is rarely sufficient because children and young people are strongly influenced by other factors, such as parents and friends (4). It should be considered and investigated how to increase teacher buy-in and how to emphasize the benefits of the strategy to the teacher to ensure their support.

National dietary guidelines as one education tool

National dietary guidelines should be a central component in promoting healthy and sustainable food consumption across the population. Institutions could advocate for science-based diets like the planetary health diet (4,5,6). If widely adopted, this diet could significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and prevent non-communicable diseases (4,5,6). Promotion strategies might include educational campaigns in schools or workplaces, mass media efforts (including social media), and collaboration with other societal stakeholders such as health insurance companies (5).

Bans and regulations

Governments can adopt bans and regulations to promote healthier behaviours, such as encouraging food reformulation. Economic strategies, including subsidies for fruits and vegetables or expanded taxation on sugar-sweetened beverages and other unhealthy foods, are also effective options (5,7). For example, in 2017, the Portuguese government introduced the EIPAS law, a ministerial strategy aimed at promoting healthy eating, which included a tax on sugar-sweetened beverages. Preliminary findings indicate that the consumption of beverages with more than 8 grams of sugar per 100 ml decreased. Revenue from this tax is allocated to public health interventions (9). Similarly, Denmark implemented a tax on high-saturated-fat foods in 2010, resulting in reduced consumption of high-fat products and increased demand for low-fat alternatives. However, this tax was repealed after just 18 months in 2012, possibly due to pressure from the food industry (10).

Retail regulation is another means of influencing consumer behaviour. This can involve banning specific food categories or imposing restrictions on their placement, price promotions, and advertising. Research suggests that removing unhealthy snacks from checkout areas leads to reduced confectionery sales (5). In October 2022, the United Kingdom enacted legislation limiting the placement of high-fat, salt, and sugar (HFSS) foods and banning multibuy offers, such as "buy one, get one free" promotions and unlimited beverage refills.

In terms of food and drink marketing, especially to children, governments are encouraged to implement WHO recommendations (1,5). Social media advertisements often go unmarked, making them difficult to identify as marketing. Children and adolescents frequently view influencers as role models, which can shape their behaviours. In 2019, Portugal introduced a law restricting the advertising of energy-dense foods and those high in salt, sugar, or fat on television, websites, social media platforms, and through influencers, using WHO monitoring protocols. However, enforcement of these restrictions is challenging and complex (5).

Research has also examined the potential positive effects of promoting food and sustainability messages via social media platforms, including blogs, influencers, and chefs. While some benefits are noted, these impacts should not be overestimated, as influencer lifestyles may not align with the everyday realities of most

individuals. Furthermore, such efforts may disproportionately affect wealthier populations and reinforce traditional gender roles in cooking practices (4).

Nudging

Everyday food purchasing is often habitual or driven by impulse, with limited effort invested in considering multiple food characteristics and their relevance for health and sustainability. Nudging strategies, such as default rules, changes in visual presentation, positioning of food, and portion sizes, can be potential options to influence consumption. Previous research indicates that nudging interventions can promote healthier food choices and encourage consumers to voluntarily contribute to environmental protection and reduce meat consumption, for example, in cafeterias (4).

Labelling

Labels serve as an important tool for decision-making. The primary challenge lies in creating labels that are both easily comprehensible and trustworthy. Once this challenge is addressed, labels can effectively guide consumers to identify sustainable products during their routine shopping activities. Third-party labels and certifications generally garner the highest level of consumer trust. However, there remains a risk of consumer confusion due to the extensive variety of labels available or a lack of understanding of the certification standards (3).

Further policy approaches

The Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI) evaluates current policies aimed at fostering healthy food environments across Europe. According to this assessment, most EU policies related to food promotion, pricing, retail, and provision are considered weak. In contrast, policies concerning nutrient declarations and health claims show moderate strength. Given their relevance to consumer behaviour and practical feasibility, the Food-EPI strongly recommends implementing the following actions: (1) front-of-packaging labels that include normative health statements and an evidence-based nutrient profiling system applicable to all food categories, both pre-packed and non-prepacked, with mandatory labelling of added sugars on pre-packed items; (2) a VAT exemption for all fresh fruits and vegetables; and (3) a ban or significant restrictions on marketing foods high in saturated fat, trans fat, salt, or added sugars to children (1).

To enable consumers to modify their food consumption behaviours, it is essential to understand these behaviours as interconnected with broader contexts and other habits. Addressing them holistically involves integrating areas like education, cultural and social factors, mobility, and food support. Adult education initiatives can include detailed food labels that provide information about product origins, production methods, and healthy diet guidelines. Awareness campaigns could highlight issues such as seasonal food availability by incorporating sustainability scores on products or offering information in retail stores (2). Interventions that account for cultural differences, social norms, and conventions influencing food choices are generally more effective in promoting sustainable changes (4).

Urban planning strategies should also support these efforts. For example, the 15-minute city concept could reduce greenhouse gas emissions by ensuring residents can access most essential services near their homes without relying on cars (2). Public initiatives to combat food poverty should prioritize sustainable options, such as distributing food vouchers for farmers' markets. Collaborations with partners like healthcare providers can further promote health and sustainability. For instance, these partners could offer classes on food skills, diet sustainability, and health or have general practitioners emphasize the importance of diet for overall well-being (2).

Adopting this comprehensive, multi-actor approach has the potential to transform beliefs and structures underlying patterns of unhealthy and unsustainable food consumption.

Good practice examples

Hungary's public health product tax, introduced in 2011, has led to moderate improvements in dietary habits, particularly among low-income households, while incentivizing companies to reformulate their recipes. The tax targets specific categories of pre-packed foods high in salt, sugar, or caffeine, and its revenue is allocated to health-improving policies. Since 2012, this revenue has been directed to the public health insurance fund, accounting for approximately 1% of its income. As a result, 40% of companies selling unhealthy foods reformulated their products, while prices for unchanged items increased by 29%, leading to a 27% reduction in sales. However, domestic companies face greater impacts from the tax compared to multinational companies, as exports are exempt (4).

The Danish Wholegrain Partnership represents a successful collaboration between public authorities, the food industry (notably the bread industry), and health NGOs to boost wholegrain consumption. Between 2004 and 2013, wholegrain intake increased by 75%, with the proportion of people meeting the recommended daily intake rising from 6% to 30%. Products bearing the wholegrain logo grew from 150 in 2009 to 800 in 2018. Public authorities played a key role by issuing dietary guidelines, creating the wholegrain product logo, and defining its criteria. The food industry responded by increasing the availability of wholegrain products that met the criteria and reformulating existing products. NGOs and authorities collaborated on educational activities and promotions with retailers, such as special offers on wholegrain products. The partnership's success was attributed to consensus on evidence and definitions, understanding consumer behaviours, tracking food trends, documenting results, and monitoring wholegrain intake consistently (4).

Denmark also boasts the most successful organic food market globally. Government intervention on both supply and demand sides facilitated the development of the organic food sector, beginning with the Danish law on organic farming in 1987 and subsequent policy adjustments in the late 1990s. Conventional retail chains also contributed by promoting organic foods early on, increasing accessibility, lowering prices, and enhancing promotion, which further boosted organic food sales (4).

In Poland, consumer cooperatives offer an innovative approach to sustainability, building on the country's historical tradition of cooperative movements from the 19th century. These cooperatives create direct connections between organized groups of consumers and small- to medium-sized local farms. By bypassing intermediaries, cooperatives ensure lower prices for high-quality food and allow farmers to benefit more from their products. Families involved in these cooperatives gain insights into sustainable food production, while farmers better understand consumer needs and expectations, helping to minimize food waste. Although the number of cooperatives continues to grow, they remain a niche phenomenon (4).

Links to policy reports

- (1) [INFORMAS Europe. \(2020\). Food – EPI.](#)
- (2) [European Commission Joint Research Centre, Bock, A., Bontoux, L., Rudkin, J. \(2022\). Concepts for a sustainable EU food system: reflections from a participatory process, Publications Office of the European Union.](#)
- (3) [European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, \(2020\). Towards a sustainable food system: moving from food as a commodity to food as more of a common good. Independent expert report.](#)
- (4) [Science Advice for Policy by European Academies \(SAPEA\). \(2020\). A sustainable food system for the European Union.](#)
- (5) [World health organization \(WHO\). \(2022\). European Regional Obesity Report 2022.](#)
- (6) [EAT. \(2020\). Diets for a better future: rebooting and reimagining healthy and sustainable food systems in the G20.](#)
- (7) [European Environmental Bureau \(EEB\). \(2022\). Hungry for change - an EU sustainable food systems law for people and nature.](#)
- (8) [Hawkes, C., Jewell, J., & Allen, K. \(2013\). A food policy package for healthy diets and the prevention of obesity and diet-related non-communicable diseases: the NOURISHING framework.](#)
- (9) [Graça, P., et al. \(2018\). A new interministerial strategy for the promotion of healthy eating in Portugal: implementation and initial results.](#)
- (10) [Jensen, J. D., & Smed, S. \(2018\). State-of-the-art for food taxes to promote public health.](#)
- (11) [World Cancer Research Fund International. \(n.d\). NOURISHING framework.](#)

An important step before designing any intervention is to clearly identify the desired outcomes, specifically the behaviours being targeted.

As a method for identifying which consumer behaviours to prioritize for the specific target group or setting, we recommend applying the High Impact Behaviour (HIB) method. The method is described in detail below.

1.3. Identify priority behaviours

Led by H4 with the support of EUFIC, the method was applied during the PLANEAT task 2.1 aiming to identify and select dietary behaviours with high impact potential that: a) had behaviour change potential (Behavioural Plasticity), b) were acceptable for target groups and stakeholders (Initiative Feasibility), and c) were within a safe operation space (regarding environmental, social, and health impacts) (Technical Potential) (Nielsen et al., 2020). Figure 4 below presents an overview of these factors and their association with each other and with high impact behaviours.

Figure 4. Factors affecting behaviour change potential

The goal was to end up with up to 5 high impact behaviours per target group. Figure 5 below shows an overview of the process of selecting these final high impact behaviours.

DIETARY BEHAVIOUR ITEMS

Figure 5. Overview of high impact behaviour selection process

As a first step, information on the country-specific dietary guidelines of each of the 9 living lab countries was collected, also capturing environmental, social and health impacts. This information was applied to create an overview of country- and target group-specific dietary behaviours. In addition, the Planetary Health Diet (Willet et al., 2019) recommendations were included to add dietary behaviours relevant to the objectives of the PLAN'EAT project. This resulted in a total of 342 dietary behaviour items.

The next step was selecting the key behaviours that would serve as the basis for the subsequent surveys, determined by two factors: a) the dietary behaviour items with the greatest consistency across dietary guidelines in the living lab countries, allowing for inclusion of the dietary behaviours considered relevant by the majority of the living lab countries and, b) inclusion of dietary behaviours relevant to the objectives of the PLANEAT project. Using this approach, 75 dietary behaviour items divided in 12 categories were determined.

To identify the final high impact behaviours, two separate surveys were created; a) one for the living lab leaders (for assessment of the *plasticity*, i.e., the likeliness that their target group would adopt the behaviour, and the *feasibility*, i.e., the likeliness that relevant stakeholders would support the target group with adopting the behaviour, of the 75 dietary behaviours identified), and b), for experts of environmental, health and socio-economic/ethical impacts (for assessment of overall or average environmental, health, or socio-economic potentials of the 75 dietary behaviours identified).

As the next step, the evaluation of the living lab ratings was linked to the evaluation of the expert ratings. Figure 6 below provides an overview of the resulting top rated 40 eating behaviours across the countries.

BEVERAGES

- B1** Drink 1.5-2L water (for an adult diet) per day
- B2** Choose tap water instead of bottled water
- B3** Choose to drink water instead of sugar-sweetened beverages
- B4** Choose to drink other unsweetened beverages (e.g., tea) instead of sugar-sweetened beverages
- B5** Choose organically produced beverages (e.g., tea, coffee, juice)
- B6** Limit alcoholic beverage consumption to a max. of up to 2 glasses/per day for men or 1 glass/per day for women
- B7** Do not drink alcohol at an age under 18 years

EGGS

- E1** Eat 2-4 servings of eggs per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 1 egg)

EATING BEHAVIOURS

- EB4** Accept a variety of foods

FISH

- F1** Eat (2-)3 servings of fish and seafood per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 125-150g)
- F3** Choose organically produced fish

FATS, SUGAR, AND SALT

- FS2** Choose vegetable oils (e.g., olive oil, rapeseed oil)
- FS3** Choose organically produced oils
- FS5** Limit the consumption of added sugars (e.g., from sweets) (max. 25 g for an adult diet per day)
- FS11** Limit consumption of processed food products high in salt, sugars, and fats (e.g., fast food, salty snacks, biscuits, bars)

GRAINS

- G1** Eat 3-6 servings of grain-based foods per day (1 serving for adult diet: e.g., 40-60 g bread/60-80 g dried pasta or rice)
- G2** Choose a variety of grain-based foods (e.g., flour types, pasta, rice etc.)
- G3** Choose primarily whole grains
- G4** Choose organically produced grains

LEGUMES

- L1** Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw/125 g cooked)
- L2** Choose a variety of legumes
- L3** Choose organically produced legumes

MEAT

- M1** Eat 0-3 servings of meat per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 100-125 g)
- M2** Limit the consumption of processed meat (both red and white meat) or even avoid it
- M3** Limit the consumption of red meat or even avoid it
- M4** Limit the consumption of all meats or even avoid it
- M5** Choose poultry instead of red/processed meat
- M9** Choose eggs instead of meat as an alternative source of protein
- M11** Choose plant-based alternatives (e.g., legumes, nuts) instead of meat as an alternative source of protein

NUTS AND SEEDS

- N1** Eat a small handful of nuts and seeds (2-)3 times a week (1 serving for an adult diet: 25 g)
- N2** Choose a variety of nuts and seeds

NUTRITIONAL NEEDS

- NN1** Know your energy (caloric) needs and eat accordingly (don't over-/under-eat)
- NN3** Ensure an adequate vitamin-D intake through sun exposure or supplementation (20 µg/d for an adult)

VEGETABLES AND FRUITS

- V1** Eat 5 servings of vegetables and fruits per day (1 serving for an adult diet: 125 g)
- V3** Choose a variety of vegetables and fruits
- V4** Choose organically produced vegetables and fruits
- V6** Choose seasonal vegetables and fruits

Figure 6. Top 40 eating behaviours

The final step involved a workshop bringing together all nine living labs with the aim of performing a final selection of a maximum of 5 high impact behaviours per country. Each living lab leader was given the option of choosing 3-5 high impact behaviours relevant for their respective target groups from a list. The most often chosen HIB were “Legumes – eat 3 servings per week) (chosen by 7), “Fruits and vegetables – eat 5 servings per day” (chosen by 6), and “Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in added fat, salt & sugar” (chosen by 5). The least chosen options were “Choose plant-based alternatives”, “Limit salt”, “Choose tap water instead of bottled water” and “Know your energy needs and eat accordingly” (each chosen by 1).

2. Understanding behaviour and developing interventions

To enable a comprehensive understanding of behaviour, the underlying factors influencing behaviour must be systematically analysed, i.e., **leverage points for behavioural change** need to be identified¹. This process ensures that behaviour change interventions are targeted and effective in addressing the specific factors determining behaviour.

Within the PLAN'EAT project, we define leverage points as entry points for interventions at the macro (food system), meso (food environment) or micro (individual) level, which can either *enable* or *constrain* changes in behaviour with high impact potential. Hence, leverage points can be barriers or enablers for specific behaviours. They can be activated through targeted interventions, i.e., concrete measures that influence e.g., societal structures, individual habits, and feedback loops within the EU food system.

For example, at the macro level, the leverage points of *societal norms* and *production systems* can be shifted with policy measures such as subsidies for sustainable agriculture or taxation of high-emission foods. At the meso level, leverage points such as *availability* and *visibility* can be improved by reshaping the food environment. For example, interventions aiming at provision and prominent placement of e.g., plant-based meals in schools or supermarkets can make sustainable choices easier for consumers. At the micro level, interventions such as *personalized dietary feedback* or prompts can target leverage points such as *self-regulation* and *habits*. Leverage points are not isolated; they are interconnected and often create cascading effects across levels. For instance, macro-level policies promoting subsidies for sustainable agriculture can increase the availability and visibility of plant-based options in food environments (meso), which in turn can support individuals in developing habits that favour sustainable dietary choices (micro). Feedback loops further reinforce these changes, where shifts in individual demand can drive broader environmental adaptations and policy shifts, fostering a dynamic system of change.

Despite these interlinkages and dynamics, the current toolbox primarily focuses on identifying micro-level leverage points, as they represent actionable opportunities for policy makers to design interventions for behaviour change. Nevertheless, where appropriate, we also address the interconnections with meso- and macro-level leverage points. The following section introduces frameworks that suggest potential leverage points and provides practical steps how to identify the most relevant in a given context, i.e., key leverage points for specific target groups. These form the base to select the most suitable strategies for behaviour change interventions.

2.1. Theory and previous research to understand behaviour

Various approaches can be utilised to achieve an understanding of leverage points, depending on the resources that are available. One low-resource approach involves consulting previous **systematic reviews to identify factors associated with specific behaviours and target groups** (e.g., Briazu et al., 2024; Graça et al., 2019; Matharu et al., 2024). Another more targeted approach entails **employing established frameworks to systematically and empirically identify factors**. Whenever resources allow, we advocate for this step, as it allows a more nuanced understanding of the most important leverage points for the specific contexts (e.g., for a specific setting or target group). For such an empirical analysis, the use of established theoretical frameworks is recommended. They provide structured methods for analysing a wide range of potential leverage points, including motivational, social, and environmental factors. This ensures that interventions are both comprehensive and tailored to the specific contexts in which a behaviour occurs.

In the following sections, two exemplary frameworks are introduced in detail, as these are the main focus of our toolbox: **The Behaviour Change Wheel (BCW) (including the COM-B model)**, and the **Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF)**. Annex F also includes the 'Determinants of Nutrition and Eating' (DONE) framework by Stok et al., 2017, which provides a comprehensive model for understanding the multifaceted factors influencing dietary behaviours by systematically categorizing 441 factors into individual, interpersonal, environmental, and policy spheres of influence. By integrating evidence from various

¹ We use the terms 'factor' and 'leverage point' interchangeably.

disciplines, the framework enables targeted interventions for diverse populations, considering modifiability, strength of evidence, and population impact for prioritizing. For more information and how practitioners can apply the DONE Framework, see Annex F.

Other frameworks can be found in the literature (e.g., Davis et al., 2015; West, Godinho et al., 2019). Further, **examples for the systematic review approach** are presented for the behaviours of general healthy eating and the behaviour of reducing meat consumption.

2.1.1. The behaviour change wheel

The BCW was created to address the need for a systematic and evidence-based framework for designing behaviour change interventions (Michie et al., 2011). It integrates insights from various theoretical models, ensuring a comprehensive and practical approach to understanding and influencing behaviour. The BCW is structured around three core layers: the **COM-B model**, which defines three categories of factors driving behaviour (Capability, Opportunity, Motivation); **intervention functions**, which are broad intervention categories including education, persuasion, incentivization, coercion, training, restriction, environmental restructuring, modelling, and enablement; and **policy categories**, which encompass policy options to deliver the intervention functions, such as guidelines, regulation, legislation, fiscal measures, service provision, communication/marketing, and environmental/social planning. This structure enables researchers and practitioners to design interventions that target specific behavioural determinants while aligning with broader systemic policies.

In the following, we present the COM-B model and the related Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF). The TDF further specifies concrete factors within the three categories of Capability, Opportunity and Motivation. The other two layers (intervention functions and policy categories) are relevant for later steps of the intervention development process and are discussed in chapter 2.3.1 'Linking key leverage points, intervention functions, policy categories and BCT's'.

The COM-B model

The COM-B model posits that behaviour (B) is influenced by three interacting categories of factors: **Capability** (C), **Opportunity** (O), and **Motivation** (M) (Michie et al., 2011). Capability refers to an individual's psychological and physical ability to perform a behaviour, including the necessary knowledge, skills, and cognitive resources. Motivation involves the internal processes that energize and direct behaviour, encompassing both reflective, conscious decision-making and automatic, emotional, and habitual responses. Opportunity, on the other hand, refers to the external physical and social factors that make the behaviour possible or prompt it, including environmental and contextual influences. The model's diagnostic value lies in its ability to identify which of these categories of factors are acting as barriers or facilitators to the desired behaviour, helping to tailor interventions that target the most relevant factors (Michie et al., 2011). Furthermore, by integrating a range of potential factors across the three categories, it ensures that behaviours are understood holistically. Within PLANEAT, the Capability and Motivation categories of factors are linked to the micro level, whereas the Opportunity category of factors focuses is more connected to the meso and macro level.

Figure 7: The COM-B model (adopted from Michie et al., 2011)

The Theoretical Domains Framework

The TDF aligns with the COM-B model’s categories, but offers a **more detailed breakdown of the potential factors determining behaviour**. Developed to unify theories of behaviour change, the TDF splits the COM-B categories further into 14 domains, which together contain 84 theoretical constructs, i.e., theory derived factors that are relevant for behaviour change. It thus provides a comprehensive lens for understanding the factors that shape behaviour (Cane et al., 2012). The 14 TDF domains and according examples are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: TDF domains linked to COM-B categories, based on Cane et al., 2012		
COM-B category	TDF Domain	Examples
Capability	Skills	I lack the cooking skills to prepare meals with alternatives to meat.
	Knowledge	I don't know what to eat instead of meat.
	Memory, Attention and Decision Processes	I find it easy to remember to eat five pieces of fruits or vegetables every day.
	Behavioural Regulation	I don't have enough willpower to not eat meat.
Opportunity	Social Influences	Important people in my life are supportive of me reducing my consumption of meat.
	Environmental Context and Resources	In most social situations, it is difficult to choose plant-based alternatives.
Motivation	Reinforcement	Reducing meat consumption feels good.
	Emotion	The situations or conditions that often exist when I eat sweet or savoury foods are when I want to cheer up.
	Social/ Professional Role and Identity	Reducing meat consumption does not suit people like me.
	Beliefs about Capabilities	Eating more fruits and vegetables than I already do would be difficult for me due to the time for preparing them.
	Optimism	I am confident that I will be able to eat more plant-based alternatives to meat.
	Intentions	I intend to reduce my meat consumption.
	Goals	I have the goal of eating 5 pieces of fruits or vegetables every day.
	Beliefs about Consequences	If I were to reduce my meat consumption, I wouldn't get all the nutrients I need.

Through this more detailed breakdown of the categories of factors of the COM-B model, the TDF allows for a more varied and precise identification of the specific factors influencing behaviour. It can be the base for

developing e.g., questionnaire to then empirically measure the importance of these factors for specific behaviours, settings and target groups.

To summarize, the BCW, COM-B and TDF function synergistically: while the BCW provides a broad, structured framework for intervention development, the COM-B offers guidance for identifying leverage points as one important step. The TDF enhances the understanding of the COM-B's individual categories of Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation, offering a deeper insight into the factors that influence behaviour and have the ability to bring about change (Michie et al., 2014).

2.1.2. Systematic review approach

The use of systematic reviews provides a valuable methodology for understanding and addressing factors influencing behaviour and identifying leverage points for change, especially **if resources such as time are short**. Systematic reviews **synthesize existing research to identify key factors**—both barriers and enablers—that affect specific dietary choices.

For example, Graça et al. (2019) utilizes a systematic review approach to investigate the **factors influencing dietary changes towards reduced meat consumption and plant-based diets**. Based on 110 relevant articles, they identify factors classified in two ways. The primary way focuses on a general synthesis of factors associated with meat curtailment, meat substitution, and adherence to a plant-based diet, aiming to identify barriers and facilitators affecting individuals' decisions and behaviours regarding meat reduction and plant-based diet adoption. Results show that factors such as *taste preferences, habit, social norms, and perceived lack of knowledge* about plant-based diets are significant barriers to reducing meat consumption. In contrast, facilitators for adopting plant-based diets include *health benefits, environmental concerns, and social support*. For example, individuals are more likely to adopt plant-based diets when they perceived these diets as beneficial for their health and the environment.

The secondary way involves classifying these factors within the broad categories of the COM-B model. Most studies focus predominantly on motivational category (93.6%), while far fewer addressed Opportunity (20%) and Capability (6.4%) categories. Motivational enablers include positive expectations about the taste of plant-based meals and increased awareness of health and environmental benefits. In the Opportunity domain, social norms often position meat as the default protein source, creating a considerable hindrance to dietary change. Prejudices against plant-based diets and lack of social support further limit opportunities for dietary change. One significant barrier in the Capability category is the lack of reliable information about plant-based nutrition and cooking skills, making it challenging for individuals to adopt dietary changes without proper support. Based on the results, Graça et al. (2019) emphasizes the need for future research to establish further empirical evidence regarding factors influencing a change in dietary behaviour, particularly focusing on Capability and Opportunity categories, which are currently underrepresented in the literature. Sociodemographic influences were also evident, with gender, age, and education identified as key variables influencing meat consumption patterns. Since study characteristics, design, sample details, and the theoretical frameworks employed are reported for each primary study, it possible to assess the applicability of the reviews results for specific contexts (such as specific target groups).

Annex G provides two further examples of literature reviews. One by Matharu et al. (2024) on consumer behaviour towards plant-based and meat-reduced diets and one by Briazu et al. (2024) on healthy diets in disadvantaged communities.

These systematic reviews exemplarily show how existing literature can be used to understand leverage points for promoting dietary change, while at the same time also pointing towards some limitations. It is important to note that such results are often not universal, and that leverage points might be different across specific contexts, i.e., types of behaviour (e.g., reducing meat consumption at home vs. reducing red meat consumption when eating out), specific target groups and settings. Therefore, the next chapter describes how to conduct research and identify leverage points for specific contexts, or if there are gaps in the literature.

Best practice to understand a behaviour is to speak to the target group of a planned intervention, as well as relevant stakeholders such as parents or teachers, and ask them about it. The subsequent sections outline the **steps for conducting research and empirically identifying leverage points** for specific behaviours and settings. Wherever possible, this tailored approach is preferable. It ensures that interventions are directly relevant and effective for the specific individuals or populations (e.g., adults, children, or teens) and contexts

2.2. (e.g. conduct research to understand behaviour) being addressed. There are multiple pathways for this step (e.g., surveys, interviews), and the following chapter provides instructions and best-practice tips how to approach each. It concludes with a case example how we implemented these steps in the PLAN'EAT project.

2.2.1. Non-divisible and end-state behaviours

To effectively analyse behaviour and identify barriers and enablers that can function as leverage points, it is essential to begin with a precise definition of the behaviour in question. The details of the behaviour need to be specified, including who engages in it, under what circumstances, and within which contexts. For instance, rather than addressing 'eating healthier or more sustainable' in general terms, in PLAN'EAT, we chose much more focused HIBs, e.g., for legumes 'Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for an adult diet: 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)' (see chapter 1.3. 'Identify priority behaviours' for more information on the HIB process). Ideally, the chosen **behaviour should be 'non-divisible' and 'end-state'** (McKenzie-Mohr, 2011). Choosing a *non-divisible* behaviour refers to defining a behaviour that is as far broken down into smaller, distinct tasks as it is still practical. E.g., the behaviour 'increasing the number of meals with legumes chosen during lunch breaks by office workers in the canteen' is very specific, ensuring clarity in identifying the unique barriers and benefits associated with it. *End-state* behaviour refers to the final action that directly achieves the desired behavioural outcome, such as eating healthily, without requiring additional steps to realise the goal. E.g., in our example above, it perhaps can be assumed that office workers most likely consume the meals they choose in a canteen setting. Nevertheless, the actual eating of the meal is the *end-state* behaviour, and studies in e.g., school canteens have shown that food waste might increase when the choice for larger volumes of fruits and vegetables is stimulated by an intervention (Gwozdz et al., 2020). Hence, it is important to define a behaviour that actually produces the desired outcome. Making sure your chosen behaviour is *non-divisible* and *end-state* creates clarity that enables targeted analysis and actionable insights.

2.2.2. Existing literature and question development

The next step involves **grounding research regarding the behaviour in question on existing literature** where possible, to ensure an efficient approach based on best practices. Reviewing studies related to the behaviour can provide valuable insights, including tested and validated question wordings that can be applied for research activities with the target group. E.g., previous literature might suggest questions to ask the target group regarding specific barriers to a behaviour. For certain behaviours, there is already a large body of evidence-based literature presenting questions that can be used to determine leverage points, e.g., for meat or fruit and vegetable consumption (Appleton et al., 2010; Erinosho et al., 2015). For other HIBs, e.g., legumes and tap water, the literature is scarcer. In this case, an adaption of existing questions from literature regarding other behaviours can be considered. Likewise, the wording in existing literature might not always be tailored to the target group in question. For example, questions might be worded addressing adults' leverage points regarding a behaviour and need to be adapted if used with children. Therefore, while it is crucial to keep question wording as equal as possible to previous research, in some applied settings smaller adaptations to the wording are unavoidable.

At this point, wherever possible, it is **beneficial to align the research approach and questions to be asked with a theoretical framework, such as the COM-B model and the TDF**, as these frameworks offer structured pathways to analyse a broad range of potential leverage points (see chapter 2.1.1. 'The Behaviour Change Wheel'). To maximise the benefit of this approach, the theoretical frameworks are covered comprehensively. For application, this means to aim at including questions covering e.g., all three categories of factors of the COM-B Model (Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation).

2.2.3. Data collection and empirical analysis

The **method of inquiry** needs to be chosen in line with the specific **needs and resources of the research project**. If the behaviour e.g., is not well researched and understood yet, or for specific target groups such as older adults, an approach with open questions might be most suitable. For example, focus groups or interviews can be a productive means of gathering qualitative data, exploring a behaviour and gaining a first solid understanding. Does the research involve sensitive topics, individual interviews or anonymous (online) surveys can be chosen to encourage honest responses. Surveys with closed questions are likewise more suitable e.g., when a set of potential barriers is well known, and the aim is to identify the most relevant ones for a specific target group. In such instances, and if resources permit, deploying surveys helps to obtain a representative understanding of barriers and enablers across a broader group of individuals from the target population. For more information and practical guidance on social science research methods, including survey design, qualitative and quantitative data analysis, see e.g. Bhattacharjee et al. (2019).

2.2.4. Key leverage points

For certain target groups and settings, potential leverage points as suggested by the literature or a theoretical framework might not pose an obstacle for behaviour change, while others might be key hindrance or enabler for the implementation of a behaviour. It is precisely these **key leverage points** that are of particular value in the development of interventions and hold potential for behavioural change (Michie et al., 2014). In the following, we therefore exemplarily describe a suggested pathway to obtain key leverage points based on a survey research approach.

Once the target group rated the survey questions, i.e., all potential leverage points have been evaluated and thus mean value calculations for each survey question across all participants are available, an approach to selecting key leverage points needs to be defined. One possible approach to differentiate between potential leverage points and key leverage points is to define cut-off points, i.e., an approach where mean value ratings above or below a certain value indicates a key leverage point. For example, when using a Likert-scale for answer ratings from 1 to 5 ('1 = Strongly disagree' to '5 = Strongly agree'), mean value ratings of 3.5 to 5 might indicate an important leverage point.

PLAN'EAT CASE STUDY

REDUCING MEAT CONSUMPTION IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS, LIVING LAB IRELAND

The following case study shows how the steps described in chapters 2.1 and 2.2 were applied in the PLAN'EAT project. It exemplarily presents results for the target group of **healthy, young university students** (aged 18-30) living in Dublin, Ireland, and studying at University College Dublin (UCD).

Non-divisible, end-state high impact behaviour: 'Meat 1 - reduce meat consumption (eat 0-3 portions/week)'

This behaviour focuses on a single specific food (meat) and an end-state behaviour (reduce consumption). The included portion information per week defines the behaviour in detail, while still providing some flexibility through the range of portions. At the same time, this behaviour still could be further broken down to make it 'more' non-divisible. For example, 'Reducing the number of meals containing meat eaten by university students in the student dormitories for dinner.' would be even more concrete. It is context dependent how detailed the behaviour should be specified. For example, it is possible to even further differentiate between the meals that students eat for dinner, when they eat alone or with their roommates, etc. At some point, there is a trade-off between helpful specificity and unnecessary narrowness.

Existing literature and question development:

A wealth of existing literature highlights potential leverage points for behaviours such as reducing meat consumption and related practices, including vegetarianism (Hielkema & Lund, 2021; Lacroix & Gifford, 2019; Rosenfeld & Tomiyama, 2020). Drawing from this foundation, we developed a survey to identify the key leverage points most relevant to the target group of UCD students. To ensure consistency and an efficient approach, the survey questions were taken from the existing literature and minimally adapted as needed. We further carefully aligned each question with the COM-B framework, and this way ensured that we cover a broad range of potential barriers with our questions.

Examples:

The survey question 'It is more of a habit to eat meat than a conscious choice' (Hielkema & Lund, 2021) aligns with COM-B 'Capability' and TDF 'Habit'.

The survey question 'In most social situations, it is easiest to eat meat' (Hielkema & Lund, 2021) aligns with COM-B 'Opportunity' and TDF 'Social norms'.

The survey question 'If I were to become a vegetarian, my diet wouldn't have enough variety' (Rosenfeld & Tomiyama, 2020) aligns with COM-B 'Motivation' and TDF 'Beliefs about consequences'.

Data collection and empirical analysis:

We used an anonymous online survey with closed questions to identify the key leverage points among the set of well-known potential leverage points from the literature research. The survey was designed using Qualtrics software and contained the following question blocks, which were specifically tailored to the target group of UCD students in terms of wording, target behaviour, and context:

- Demographic information such as age, gender, highest level of education, dietary restrictions
- General questions about usual eating habits (Ahrens et al., 2017), and food neophobia (Ritchey et al., 2003; Pliner & Hobden, 1992)
- Food frequency questionnaire (Lanfer et al., 2011)
- Leverage point questions on different HIBs: meat, HFSS, fruits and vegetables, legumes, and energy needs

Annex H Table 1 provides an overview of answers to all survey question, i.e., potential leverage points, which were asked to investigate the target behaviour meat reduction.

The online survey was answered by 156 participants from this target group, while the number of participants who fully answered the questions on the leverage points for meat reduction is 122.

Key leverage points:

For the selection of key leverage points, cut-off points were defined for the Likert-scale answer categories at 3.5 or higher. The numbers marked in red in Annex H Table 1 for the items 'Following a diet with reduced meat consumption takes extra time and effort.', 'It is more of a habit to eat meat than a conscious choice.', and 'People I live with do not want to reduce their meat consumption.' represent the key leverage points found when using these cut-off points.

As shown in Figure 8, we separated consumers into **three different groups based on their current consumption of foods relevant for the HIB**, i.e., low, medium or high adherence group. These consumer groups, derived from participants' responses to the food frequency questionnaire, aim to better understand the barriers different consumer groups face towards adopting the HIB. **High adherence to the HIB** means that the consumption of the participant already corresponds very well with the target behaviour (e.g., a person that already consumes meat and meat products 0 times per week). On the contrary, **low adherence to the HIB** means that the consumption of the participant does not correspond with the target behaviour (e.g., a person that consumes meat and meat products more than 4 times per week). **Medium adherence to the HIB** means that the consumption of the participant corresponds with the target behaviour to some degree, but there is still potential to increase adherence to the HIB (e.g., a person that consumes meat and meat products between 1 and 4 times per week).

In our example, the number of participants in the adherence groups is distributed as follows: low adherence n: 74, medium adherence n: 23, and high adherence n: 25. (Total n: 122). Whenever key leverage points were identified for at least one of the adherence groups, the following graphs were created. The dotted line represents the cut-off for key leverage points.

Figure 8. Key leverage points of the LL Ireland for Meat1.

For the HIB reducing meat consumption (0-3 portions/week), we identified key leverage points across all three adherence groups. The low adherence group states **extra time and effort as a main barrier** to eating a diet with less meat, and both the low and medium adherence groups indicate that **people in their household do not want to reduce meat consumption**. Interestingly, the high adherence group, i.e., consumers that already eat little or no meat, indicate that **meat eating as a habit** is a key leverage point. This might be their assessment of possible leverage points meat eaters have, or it might mean that they only eat meat habitually on very rare occasions (such as e.g., festive events).

2.2.5. Systemic perspective

Lastly, we want to reiterate the importance of a systemic perspective to thoroughly understand dietary behaviours. **Leverage points exist at three different levels - at the micro (individual), meso (food environment), and macro level (food system).** The current toolbox focuses on the micro level, and hence describes strategies to obtain key leverage points and plan interventions that are intended to achieve consumer behaviour change. It takes one of many perspectives, i.e., that the individual consumer at the micro level can be the pivotal point for change through their consumption choices.

However, there are multiple further **food system actors** that significantly influence dietary behaviours. In this context it is important to emphasise that the immense shift needed for healthier and more sustainable diets across Europe, as is the approach of the PLAN'EAT project, cannot be the responsibility of consumers alone, but that behavioural change must also be facilitated at the other levels (Boulet et al., 2021). After all, consumer decisions are embedded in their environment, and environments are influenced by macrosocial factors such as policies and norms. Hence, the development of promising intervention strategies requires a **systemic perspective that considers leverage points and actors at all these levels simultaneously** (Hitt et al., 2007).

For example, the choice of food and meals depends heavily on availability, accessibility, and affordability, which are influenced by actors in the food system such as retailers or canteens (meso level). These are in turn influenced by regulatory and social frameworks, culture and traditions, and by e.g., policy makers and industry stakeholders (macro level). Deliverable D2.5 'Synthesis report on factors influencing dietary behaviour at micro, meso and macro levels' of the PLANEAT project discusses this aspect in much more detail, and presents many more examples across different HIBs and leverage points.

The empirical approach to identifying key leverage points described in this chapter spans both the micro and meso levels, as the methods described are equally applicable. For example, the COM-B model covers both micro and meso leverage points. Leverage points at macro level are not addressed by this model. However, a similar research approach as described here, including literature research as well as quantitative or qualitative methods, such as stakeholder workshops and interviews, is also appropriate for the macro level.

2.3. Finding suitable intervention strategies

After identifying the key leverage points that influence behaviour, the next crucial step is to choose behaviour change strategies that effectively address these key leverage points. This chapter explores **approaches for determining the most favourable courses of action to address the key leverage points**. Specifically, the application of the BCW framework and associated BCTs will be explained, as well as the utilization of the Theory and Techniques Tool. These methodologies provide **systematic pathways for translating insights about key leverage points into practical interventions**. In addition, the use of evidence-based literature is discussed as a further approach.

2.3.1. Linking key leverage points, intervention functions, policy categories and BCT's

The **BCW** (see chapter 2.1.1 'The Behaviour Change Wheel') offers a systematic framework for designing behaviour change interventions (see Figure 9). It suggests **three interrelated stages for intervention development**.

1. **Stage 1:** select the target behaviour and identify which key leverage points need to change to achieve desired behaviour change outcome.
2. **Stage 2:** identify the most suitable intervention functions and policy categories that address the identified leverage points.
3. **Stage 3:** identifying content and implementation options (e.g., BCTs that align with the chosen intervention functions and further intervention characteristics, e.g., mode of delivery).

Figure 9. The Behaviour Change Wheel, from Michie et al., 2011

Stage 1 is described in previous chapters (see chapter 2.1 'Theory and previous research to understand behaviour' and chapter 2.2 'Conduct research to understand behaviour' for a detailed description). Concrete steps to take for Stage 2 and 3 are described in the following.

Intervention functions and policy categories (stage 2)

The goal of stage 2 is to **map the identified key leverage points to intervention functions and policy categories**. Intervention functions outline the types of interventions through which behaviour change can be facilitated (e.g., education, incentives, or persuasion). Policy categories represent the broader systemic or societal measures (e.g., regulation, service provision, or legislation) that support or enable the implementation of these interventions.

Table 3 and Table 4 show an overview over intervention functions and policy categories, as well as their linkages with COM-B categories. This overview ensures that leverage points identified via COM-B diagnosis are systematically linked to suitable intervention functions. These are further supported by policies, creating an integrated and actionable behaviour change intervention strategy. The links between COM-B, TDF, and BCW intervention functions were established through a consensus exercise conducted by a group of experts.

INTERVENTION FUNCTIONS		EDUCATION	PERSUASION	INCENTIVISATION	COERCION	TRAINING	RESTRICTION	ENVIRONMENTAL RESTRUCTURING	MODELLING	ENABLEMENT
COM-B COMPONENTS	PHYSICAL CAPABILITY									
PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPABILITY										
PHYSICAL OPPORTUNITY										
SOCIAL OPPORTUNITY										
AUTOMATIC MOTIVATION										
REFLECTIVE MOTIVATION										

INTERVENTION FUNCTIONS		EDUCATION	PERSUASION	INCENTIVISATION	COERCION	TRAINING	RESTRICTION	ENVIRONMENTAL RESTRUCTURING	MODELLING	ENABLEMENT
POLICY CATEGORIES	COMMUNICATION/ MARKETING									
GUIDELINES										
FISCAL MEASURES										
REGULATION										
LEGISLATION										
ENVIRON/SOCIAL PLANNING										
SERVICE PROVISION										

Table 3. Matrix of links between interventions functions and COM-B, from Michie et al., 2014

Table 4. Matrix of links between intervention functions and policy categories, from Michie et al., 2014

Behaviour Change Techniques (stage 3)

Next, the aim is to determine which BCTs can most effectively deliver the intervention functions identified in the previous step, while ensuring they align with the relevant policy categories. This step marks a critical transition from identifying what needs to be addressed to **specifying how** it can be achieved through **targeted techniques** (Michie et al., 2014).

BCTs are defined as ‘**observable, replicable, and irreducible components of an intervention designed to alter or redirect causal processes that regulate behaviour**’. BCTs function as the ‘active ingredients’ of interventions by operationalising the broader intervention functions into actionable strategies. This ensures that the selected intervention functions are translated into specific, evidence-based techniques capable of directly influencing behaviour (Michie et al., 2013). The *Behaviour Change Technique Taxonomy (v1)* (BCT taxonomy v1) provides a widely recognised and standardised framework for classifying and describing these techniques across disciplines and study designs (Marques et al., 2024). The taxonomy outlines 93 distinct BCTs, which are systematically organised into 16 higher-order categories based on their functional roles. For example, the category *goals and planning* includes specific techniques such as goal setting (outcome), goal setting (behaviour), and commitment. This standardized approach ensures consistency in the design, implementation, and evaluation of interventions, enabling researchers and practitioners to compare and synthesize findings more effectively across contexts (Michie et al., 2013, 2015).

To narrow down the selection of BCTs, it is useful to first **consider those most frequently associated with the chosen intervention functions**. If *Education* is selected as an intervention function, relevant BCTs might include providing *information about the consequences of a behaviour* or offering *instruction on how to perform a specific behaviour*. Annex I includes an overview over the most and less frequently used BCTs for each intervention function. This approach, alongside the APEASE criteria (see box below), helps streamline the selection process by focusing initially on frequently used BCTs before considering less commonly applied ones (Michie et al., 2014).

A helpful tool for stages 2 and 3 of the BCW: The APEASE criteria

The **APEASE criteria** are a helpful tool for decision-making throughout stages 2 and 3 of the BCW (Michie et al., 2014). This framework provides a structured approach to selecting and evaluating intervention strategies, ensuring that they are not only effective but also feasible, appropriate, and equitable. The APEASE criteria consist of six considerations: **A**ffordability, **P**racticability, **E**ffectiveness and cost-effectiveness, **A**ceptability, **S**ide-effects/safety, and **E**quity. Effectiveness is often the primary focus when designing behaviour change interventions. However, the APEASE framework emphasizes the need to **balance effectiveness with other practical considerations**. For example, **affordability** evaluates whether an intervention can be delivered within budgetary constraints and made accessible to all relevant beneficiaries. Closely related, **cost-effectiveness** assesses the ratio of benefits to costs, ensuring rational resource allocation. If two interventions are equally effective, the more cost-effective option is preferred; if one is more effective but less cost-effective, affordability becomes a decisive factor. **Practicability** assesses whether an intervention can realistically be implemented using available resources and delivery mechanisms. For instance, an intervention requiring specialized staff and extensive resources may succeed under controlled conditions where conditions are ideal but may fail in an everyday setting where such resources and expertise are often limited. Acceptability considers the perspectives of various stakeholders—ranging from policymakers to the target population—acknowledging that perceptions may vary based on cultural, political, or ethical factors. Meanwhile, side-effects or safety concerns evaluate unintended consequences that might undermine the intervention's overall benefit. Finally, equity examines whether the intervention reduces disparities in health and well-being across different societal groups or exacerbates inequalities.

The APEASE criteria are recommended for use at multiple decision points within the BCW. They guide the identification of intervention functions, policy categories, BCTs, and modes of delivery. By applying the APEASE criteria, decision-makers can ensure that each choice is aligned with the intervention's effectiveness and feasibility, (Michie et al., 2014).

2.3.2. The theory and techniques tool

The [Theory and Techniques Tool](#) is an interactive resource designed to assist researchers and practitioners in identifying effective behaviour change strategies. By leveraging the Theory and Techniques Tool, intervention developers can make **well-informed decisions about which BCTs to implement**, ensuring a strong **empirical foundation** and enhancing the effectiveness of behaviour change intervention.

It systematically maps the relationships between BCTs and their mechanisms of action (MoAs)²—the processes through which these techniques influence behaviour. The online tool presents a heat map featuring 74 BCTs and 26 MoAs, yielding 1924 possible connections. Each cell illustrates the strength of a specific BCT-MoA relationship, visualised through colour gradients. Users can interact with the heat map to examine these associations in detail and access supporting data from the studies analysed, providing valuable insights for intervention design.

The Theory and Techniques Tool can be applied to, for example, the PLAN'EAT case study data on reducing meat consumption among university students at Living Lab Ireland, as outlined in chapter 2.2 'Conduct research to understand behaviour'. The following steps describe the process:

1. One identified key leverage point is *'It's more of a habit to eat meat than a conscious choice'*.
2. This key leverage point can be mapped to one or more MoAs. Applicable MoAs are:
 - motivation (i.e., 'processes relating to the impetus that gives purpose or direction to behaviour, operating at both conscious and unconscious levels'),

² Note that MoAs are similar to leverage points, but they are not necessarily the same. While leverage points point towards barriers or enabler for a behaviour, MoAs are the processes or pathways through which behaviour change strategies influence behaviour. In short, leverage points are the strategic 'targets' for change (e.g., a lack of knowledge to be addressed at the micro, meso and macro level), while MoAs are the 'tools' and processes through which change is achieved (e.g., an increase in knowledge for an individual leads them to change their behaviour).

- memory and attention or
 - environmental context (e.g., focusing awareness on non-meat options in the environment).
3. According to the Tool, the following BCTs are strongly linked to the MoA motivation:
 - Goal setting (outcome)
 - Feedback on behaviour
 - Pros and cons
 - Incentive (outcome), Reward (outcome), and Self-talk.
 - A strategy that links to both memory and attention as well as environmental context are prompts and cues.
 4. Based on this preselection of BCTs, and together with the APEASE criteria (see box above), a decision can be made regarding the most suitable options for the context of the planned intervention.

Similarly, the statement *'People I live with do not want to reduce their meat consumption'*, which belongs to the Opportunity category of the COM-B model, also represents a key leverage point. In this case, the following MoAs can be considered: Social influences (interpersonal processes that influence changes in thoughts, feelings, or behaviours), Norms (the attitudes and behaviours exhibited by others within a social group), and Subjective Norms (one's perceptions of what others within a social group believe and do). Suitable BCTs for each of these MoAs can then be identified using the [Theory and Technique Tool](#).

2.3.3. Existing scientific evidence

Next to applying the tools described above, it is also possible to **incorporate existing literature evidence**, ideally from reviews and meta-analyses when available. Successful intervention strategies from previous interventions, possibly from different settings or target groups, can be identified and adapted to the current intervention objectives. In this way, the risk of ineffective interventions can be reduced by applying proven strategies. For instance, Grundy et al. (2022) present evidence of **successful intervention strategies for meat reduction behaviours** in a systematic review. In the target group of middle-aged adults (general population) a tailored approach involving individual lifestyle counselling appears promising. Evidence from the review supports this approach, with six out of eight studies favouring interventions that provide individualized supporting materials. These materials include information on barriers to change, feedback, and support mechanisms to prompt behaviour change (Grundy et al., 2022). Another review by Bianchi et al. (2018) investigates the effectiveness of environmental restructuring interventions aimed at reducing the demand for meat. For example, reducing portion sizes of meat in both restaurant and laboratory settings appears a promising strategy, supported by findings of three crossover randomised controlled trials. Conversely, manipulating the labels or description of meat or meat alternatives at the point of purchase appears less promising, with only one of five interventions providing evidence of effectiveness.

Another way of choosing intervention strategies is to draw on **best practice examples from research projects**. For example, within the Food4Me project, participants who received personalized diet and lifestyle advice were eating significantly healthier than control participants who received non-personalised, population-based advice after an intervention period of six months (Celis-Morales et al, 2017). In the European Eatwell project, different public information campaigns in the United Kingdom, Denmark and Spain led to an increase in fruit and vegetable consumption (e.g., the five-a-day campaign), and to a reduction in salt consumption, with the effects being stronger for women than for men (Traill et al., 2013).

Overall, it is recommended to use existing scientific literature if there is robust, well-documented evidence, such as reported effect sizes, clearly described intervention content and successful implementation, supporting the effectiveness of the intervention. However, potential **limitations of the reviews** and their underlying original studies should always be considered, such as variations in review quality, differences in study designs and outcome variables (Shea et al., 2017). Likewise, it should be critically assessed whether it is possible and appropriate to transfer intervention strategies which have been tested in potentially different contexts (i.e., with different target groups or in different settings) to other contexts.

Therefore, especially in the absence of sufficient literature and evidence, such as for behavioural interventions targeting older adults (Lara et al., 2014; Zaslavsky et al., 2022), it may be beneficial to use a proven methodological approach, strategy or model, as outlined in the previous two sections. As these approaches provide a clear and transparent framework for developing an intervention strategy directly tailored to the target group and setting in the current context.

PLAN'EAT CASE STUDY

INCREASING LEGUMES CONSUMPTION IN CHILDREN, LIVING LAB POLAND

Within the PLAN'EAT project, the following target behaviour was selected for the target group of **children** (aged 1-16) living in Poland who are healthy and have a **low socio-economic status**: 'Legumes - Eat 3 servings of legumes per week (1 serving for a children's diet: age appropriate up to 70 g raw / 125 g cooked)'.

Linking key leverage points and intervention function to BCT's:

As a starting point to develop a tailored behaviour change strategy, we used one of the identified **key leverage points** namely 'My child does not have the habit of eating legumes.' (see Annex H, Table 2). This key leverage point aligns with 'Motivation' (COM-B) and 'Habit' (TDF). Hence, there are a variety of suitable and proven intervention functions according to the BCW framework, such as education, incentives, environmental restructuring, and enablement (see Table 5).

Table 5. Indicative mapping of intervention functions to COM-B targets, by West, Michie et al., 2019.

	CAPABILITY	OPPORTUNITY	MOTIVATION
EDUCATION	✓		✓
PERSUASION			✓
INCENTIVES			✓
COERCION			✓
TRAINING	✓	✓	✓
RESTRICTION		✓	
ENVIRONMENTAL RESTRUCTURING		✓	✓
MODELLING		✓	✓
ENABLEMENT	✓	✓	✓

To carefully consider **which intervention function is best suited to the context** (i.e., the target group of children and a school setting), the LL leaders who have an in-depth understanding of this context were consulted. Through the LL approach, 'Enablement' was selected alongside 'Education', as these two are considered the most practical and cost-effective to achieve the desired behaviour change in this context. The intervention function 'Enablement', which is the focus of this case example, is defined as follows: 'Providing support to improve ability to change in a variety of ways not covered by other intervention functions.' (West, Michie et al., 2019, p. 25). It can be delivered most effectively using the BCTs listed in Table 6:

Table 6. Linking intervention functions to BCTs, by Michie et al., 2014

Intervention function	Individual BCTs
Enablement	<p>Most frequently used BCTs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social support (unspecified) • Social support (practical) • Goal setting (behaviour) • Goal setting (outcome) • Adding objects to the environment • Problem solving • Action planning • Self-monitoring of behaviour • Restructuring the physical environment • Review behaviour goal(s) • Review outcome goal(s)

Using the LL approach, the BCTs ‘Goal setting’ and ‘Self-monitoring’ were then selected, as these two are considered to be the most promising to directly influence target behaviour.

Goal setting: formulating goals such as ‘On day [X] I am going to shop the groceries for the legumes dish. I am going to cook the dish on day [Y]’. When formulating these goals, picking the recipe and preparing the shopping list for it would provide further support to improve the ability to change and facilitate the actual realisation of the goal by the participants.

Note: The placeholders, which indicate the planned implementation days at which the goal setting is aimed, should be determined individually by the parents of the targeted children in order to facilitate application in their everyday family lives.

Self-monitoring: e.g., using a notebook or an app to tick off the legume dishes cooked each week to further motivate implementation

These two strategies can be concretised through e.g., a targeted literature search identifying effective examples from previous interventions and in collaboration with the LL leaders.

2.4. Propose concrete intervention

Once the most promising strategies are identified, the **exact implementation of these strategies** in an intervention must be planned. Key questions that need to be answered regard the **setting** (e.g., place and time) of intervention implementation, **delivery modes and sources** for intervention material and further details. Carefully considering and reporting these aspects is not only crucial for intervention success, but also for reporting of interventions and sharing obtained insights with the wider research and policy community. Only if these aspects are well reported is it possible for future efforts to build on previous results, and to increase our shared understanding of ‘*What works, compared with what, how well, with what exposure, with what behaviours (for how long), for whom, in what settings and why?*’ (Michie et al., 2017). The following sections introduces frameworks for planning concrete intervention components, including co-creation approaches.

2.4.1. Developing all aspects of an intervention

The AACTT (Action, Actor, Context, Target, Time) framework (Presseau et al., 2019) is an approach developed to specify behaviours in healthcare interventions, and it can also be applied when planning intervention components above and beyond BCTs. In the following, we provide definitions for each of the components of the AACTT framework, as well as examples of how to apply them to intervention development:

- Action: a discrete observable behaviour, i.e., the content of an intervention, including the exact specification of the BCTs used and their precise implementation. This also includes the way in which the intervention material is presented, such as digitally or in person
 - e.g., an informational talk about the health benefits of fruits and vegetables presented orally
- Actor: The person or group carrying out the Action, i.e., the person who carries out the intervention
 - e.g., a healthcare provider
- Context: The social and physical environment in which the intervention takes place
 - e.g., in a school environment
- Target group: The specific group at which the intervention is aimed
 - e.g., young children
- Time: Time and duration of the intervention, including schedules and timetables
 - e.g., once per week, repeatedly over the course of four weeks

Another valuable source for researchers and practitioners to design, evaluate, and replicate interventions with greater precision is the **Behaviour Change Intervention Ontology (BCIO)** (Michie et al., 2017; Michie et al., 2021; www.bciontology.org) (see Figure 10 for a depiction of BCIO components). It partially overlaps with the AACTT framework but offers a more in-depth approach to specifying intervention components.

Figure 10. Initial schematic of upper-level Behaviour Change Intervention Ontology: scenario entities and causal connections, from Michie et al, 2021

For the purpose of this toolbox, the BCIO can help us identify **which aspects of an intervention, beyond BCTs, require detailed and explicit planning**. The following sections explain each BCIO component in detail. Applying the BCIO—carefully considering each component during intervention planning and thoroughly describing them during reporting—ensures clarity and consistent descriptions across studies. This improves the ability to compare, replicate, and adapt interventions for different contexts or populations. Furthermore, it supports evidence synthesis, interdisciplinary collaboration, and advanced data analysis, ultimately enabling more effective and scalable solutions.

1. The **Intervention** aimed at influencing behaviour, including its
 - a. Content: the content of the intervention (e.g., the BCT goal setting) and, if applicable, the dose or amount of intervention content delivered (e.g., the number of further BCTs, such as information provision)
 - b. Delivery
 - *Mode of delivery*: medium or channels that are used to deliver the content of a BCI (e.g., oral presentations)
 - *Intervention source*: who delivers the BCI (e.g., a health professional)
 - *Schedule of delivery*: the timing and patterning of delivery of activities that make up the content of the BCI (e.g., an intervention duration of two sessions)
 - *Style of delivery*: the manner in which the content of a BCI is delivered (e.g., cold and distant versus warm and accepting communication style)
 - c. Tailoring: personalising of content; can be static (i.e., conducted before intervention delivery), or dynamic (i.e., conducted one or more times after the intervention has started in a given case based on population or setting characteristics present at that time) (e.g., real-time adaption of intervention content to current emotional states of recipients)
2. The **Exposure** to the intervention, which contains both
 - a. Reach: percent of a target population who are exposed to the intervention (e.g., reaching 5% of parents of a school with educational sessions)
 - b. Engagement: actual participation in the BCI (e.g., 80% of parents in the educational sessions are actively listening, and 50% are doing the homework)

Considering potential obstacles towards exposure during intervention, planning can help to think about implementation approaches that increase the exposure to the intervention.

3. The **Context** in which the intervention takes place, including:
 - a. *Populations*: intervention target group (e.g., children in the EU aged 6-12 years who do not eat 5 pieces of fruit or vegetables per day for at least a year)
 - b. *Settings*: locations, environment and facilities in which the behaviour change intervention is delivered (e.g., school canteen, physicians' offices),
 - c. *Events*: other relevant that may be taking place at the time of the intervention (e.g., Covid-19 pandemic)
4. The **Mechanisms of action**, i.e., the processes through which interventions may influence behaviour (e.g., increasing awareness of the health benefits of fruits and vegetables or habits for eating them). Interventions are developed to target specific leverage points and mechanisms of action (see chapter 2.3.2 'The Theory and Techniques tool'), and clearly defining, measuring and reporting these is crucial for knowledge accumulation about what works and why.
5. The **Behaviour** of interest, clearly defined as non-divisible and end-state (see chapter 2.2.1 'Non-divisible and end-state behaviours') (e.g., intake of minimum 5 fruits and vegetables per day)
6. The **Outcome**, i.e., the outcomes that are recorded in terms of the target behaviour (e.g., 10% of parents report that their child reaches an intake of 5 fruit and vegetable per day). Considering this component early in the intervention development process means reflecting on potential pathways to measure intervention success.

Lastly, checklists such as the [TiDier checklist](#) and the [CONSORT statement](#) are valuable tools for ensuring the comprehensive and standardized reporting of interventions (Hoffmann et al., 2014; Moher et al., 2001). Likewise, the [Paper Authoring Tool](#) (PAT) is an example of a tool that supports researchers and practitioners in designing their reports appropriately. In the future, the widespread application of such tools will ensure that interventions reports are transparent and interventions reproducible, and that evidence can be easily synthesised and better adapted to specific contexts.

2.4.2. Intervention co-creation and personalisation

An effective way to enhance the feasibility of an intervention for a target group is to **involve them directly in shaping the implementation plan** that best suits their needs. This can be achieved through co-creation, such as workshops with a small group of participants representative of the target group. In these workshops, participants provide feedback on initial implementation ideas or specific aspects, as well as suggest additional ideas. This input helps refine and improve the intervention design, ensuring it aligns more closely with the target group's needs and preferences (Crawford et al., 2002; Durand et al., 2014; Martin et al., 2005). Co-creation, however, does not always require direct input from the target group; it can also involve stakeholders interested in the implementation or researchers conducting the study. According to Leask et al. (2019), **co-creation is an iterative process** involving a recursive learning cycle of planning, conducting, reflecting, evaluating, and revising the design (see Figure 11). The authors also provide a checklist for reporting co-creation efforts based on these components.

Figure 11. Iterative co-creation process, from Leask et al., 2019

To adopt a more individualised approach to co-creation, it may be beneficial to give participants a degree of **autonomy in shaping certain aspects of the intervention individually**. For example, participants could decide when and how often they personally want to receive *prompts* on their mobile devices that encourage consuming at least five servings of fruits and vegetables. Further, allowing participants to set personalised goals tailored to their daily routines—such as specifying their own target for fruit and vegetable consumption—may be more effective than applying uniform, one-size-fits-all guidelines. This personalisation can be implemented in a static way, with goals set once at the start of the intervention. Alternatively, with modern technology like smartphone apps, it can be dynamic, adapting in real-time based on data generated by the participant during the intervention (Chevance et al., 2020; Korinek et al., 2018). Such personalised approaches enhance the relevance, motivation, and feasibility of interventions for each participant. As a result, tailored interventions are associated with higher success rates, improved health outcomes, and more sustainable behaviour changes (Chevance et al., 2020; Hekler et al., 2020; Moskow et al., 2023).

2.4.3. Intervention pre-test

If time and resources are available, it is always advisable to **test the intervention strategy on a small scale**, e.g., in a pilot study, in order to evaluate the effect and, if necessary, optimize the design of the intervention before actual implementation (see chapter 3). This allows the intervention strategy to be flexibly adapted to the target group and the given circumstances (Voss et al., 2020).

PLAN'EAT CASE STUDY

REDUCING HFSS CONSUMPTION IN ELDERLY PEOPLE, LIVING LAB GREECE

Within the PLAN'EAT project, the following target behaviour was defined for the target group of **elderly people (aged > 60)** living in Attica, Greece, who are free-living (not hospitalized or institutionalized) and who have risk factors for non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as dyslipidaemia, hypertension, (pre-)diabetes and/or obesity: 'HFSS – Limit the consumption of ultra-processed food products high in added fat, salt & sugar'.

For this HIB, we identified the following **key leverage points** 'I eat sweet or savoury foods when I am hungry.', 'I eat sweet or savoury foods when I have tempting foods in front of me.', and 'I choose sweet or savoury foods because it is good value for money.'. Following the LL approach, we also identified the leverage point 'I eat sweet or savoury foods when I engage in sedentary activities such as watching TV, watching movies, reading, and surfing the Internet.' as key leverage point³. The identified key leverage points align with 'Capability' and 'Motivation' (COM-B) (see Annex H Table 3).

The **intervention functions** 'education' and 'restructuring of the environment' were selected according to the BCW framework. The intervention function 'Environmental restructuring', which is the focus of this case example, is defined as follows: 'Constraining or promoting behaviour by shaping the physical or social environment.' (West, Michie et al., 2019, p. 25). Using the LL approach, the **BCTs 'Restructuring the physical environment', 'Adding objects to the environment', and 'Prompts/cues'** were selected. The actionable strategy was concretised through targeted literature research and the LL approach and designed as follows.

Examples for most promising strategies:

- **Environmental Restructuring:** Replacement of unhealthy snacks high in fat, sugar, and salt with fruits and vegetables at home. Provision of healthier snacks (fruits & vegetables) within sight of where the participant usually is snacking. Removal of unhealthy snacks from visible places (Carels et al., 2014; Johnson et al., 2020; Rothman et al., 2009).
- **Prompts/cues:** Usage of reminder stickers placed on high-used items, such as remote controls, cabinets, snack containers, or fridge (Papies & Veling, 2013; van Leeuwen et al., 2019).
Preparing a shopping list with healthier snacks and placing a reminder sticker to avoid buying unhealthy snacks could provide further support to improve the ability to change and facilitate the actual realisation of the strategy by the participants.

Develop all aspects of the intervention:

The components of the AACTT framework developed by Penseu et al. (2019) were defined as follows:

- **Action:** Restructuring of the environment and prompts/cues (see the exact strategy described above) to modify the home environment of the elderly people. The intervention material, i.e., the reminder stickers, are physically provided. These are co-created with the participants during an initial face-to-face nutrition education consultation at the beginning of the intervention.
- **Actor:** The target group of elderly people themselves and, if applicable, the person who does the grocery shopping for the participants. The nutrition education consultation is carried out by a nutritionist-dietician.
- **Context:** Mainly in the participants' homes. In addition, in places where the food is bought (supermarket, farmers market, ...) when using the prepared shopping list. The nutrition education consultation takes place at Harokopeio University.
- **Target group:** Elderly people (aged > 60) living in Attica, Greece, who are free-living (not hospitalized or institutionalized) and who have risk factors for non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as dyslipidaemia, hypertension, (pre-)diabetes and/or obesity
- **Time:** The intervention runs for 16 weeks from June-October 2025. Pre- and post-measures are carried out at the beginning and end of the intervention as part of the two nutrition education consultations. The consultations last about 1-1 ½ hours each.

³ Despite its mean value rating being 3.2, which means it is slightly below the cut-off limit of 3.5 for key leverage points

Intervention Co-Creation:

In order to apply a tailored and **individualised approach** and engage participant in the intervention, we encourage the participants in the first nutrition education consultation to design a reminder sticker themselves containing a personalized message (there will be guidelines from the literature and possibly a small selection of pre-designed stickers to choose from or to use as a template). They should state why they have chosen which sticker, how many they want to place and where they want to place them. They are encouraged to place the stickers where they think they make the most sense to facilitate the target behaviour. In the second nutrition education consultation there will be follow-up questions about the reminder stickers (Glover et al., 2012).

Example sticker reminders (pre-designed using the LL approach):

- 'Pause – Are you really hungry?'
- 'Is this your best choice?'
- 'Choose fruits and veggies over snacks.'

In addition, a tailored approach to environmental restructuring is applied by having participants replace unhealthy snacks with healthy snacks at home, deciding where exactly the placement is most beneficial to achieve behaviour change and why. In the second nutrition education consultation there will be follow-up questions about the location of replacement.

3. Planning the impact

The main aim of this chapter is to describe how to plan the impact of interventions. It is meant as a sort of check list that policymakers and researchers can follow. Planning the impact is crucial to establish a dialogue between policymakers and researchers to improve eating behaviours and develop effective tools. Researchers provide scientific data and in-depth analyses of eating behaviours, while policymakers can share and act on information about current policies and the needs of the population. This collaboration allows for the combination of theory and practice to create more relevant solutions.

Policymakers can use research to develop scientifically based policies that are more likely to succeed. This ensures that interventions are effective and adapted to real-world conditions. By working together, policymakers and researchers can explore new ideas and approaches to improve eating behaviours. This synergy can lead to innovative solutions that might not have been considered otherwise.

Policymakers have experience in implementing policies and can provide feedback on the feasibility of researchers' recommendations. This allows for the adjustment of strategies to make them more easily applicable and accepted by the population. Continuous collaboration enables the monitoring of the impact of implemented policies and the adjustment of strategies based on the results obtained. Researchers can help evaluate the effectiveness of interventions and propose improvements.

In this chapter, the following parts will be presented:

1. Guidelines for better defining impact measurement as part of action research to facilitate dialogue between policymakers and researchers
2. Recommendations for defining the measures of success of the impacts
3. Recommendations for trial intervention
4. Guidelines and methodologies for evaluating and adapting impact: using quantitative and qualitative indicators, mixed methods trailing and seeing whether the success measure has been accomplished
5. Sharing findings at the right scale to impact the behaviour and be adapted to people's territories.

3.1. Planning the impact in a participative-research context

3.1.1. Why plan the impact?

According to the FAO (Dufour, Breyné, 2011), impact assessment is fundamental, but represents a major investment. It must therefore be well planned. Human and financial resources required for its success must also be planned and mobilized. And the results must be communicated to be used.

That is why planning the impact is necessary:

- In a context of limited financial resources, policymakers support programs financially, if they are increasingly based on the effectiveness of the results brought about by the intervention.
- Stakeholders need information on the impact of interventions to strengthen their actions and roles in the food system.
- Knowing the effectiveness of programs encourages ethical validation of their implementation (hence the importance for living labs of having this approval for the interventions developed).

It is important to differentiate between the evaluation of the intervention and the evaluation of its impact. Carrying out an intervention means expecting it to have an impact. Thus, expected impact measurement or evaluation can help to understand both what works to change behavior and what works to address the reason it is necessary to change it (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021).

The following diagram illustrates the various steps required to achieve impact measurement (Dufour, Breyne, 2011) (Figure 12):

1. **Strategies, resources, HIB, needs:** these first steps are designed as explained in previous chapters 1 and 2. They are essential to determine the feasibility and implementation criteria for a program, a policy or an intervention. Measure the effectiveness of interventions with a view to improve it and compare the effectiveness of different approaches/projects.
2. **Interventions implemented:** here it is evaluated whether program activities are carried out as planned, if they must be monitored, particularly if a co-creation process has been initiated (see chapter 2.4.2).
3. **Results:** this stage highlights what the intervention directly produced (e.g. satisfaction of participants, teaching tools for the target group, etc.). It measures whether the intervention has achieved its intended results, and which planned or readapted process has been implemented.
4. **Effects:** the aim of this stage is to determine if the activities have produced the expected results according to the interaction function chosen, or, in another way, what the intervention intends to change (e.g. new knowledges, answering the needs, etc.).
5. **Impact:** this final step consists in assessing the program's effectiveness, if behaviors really changed over time. It also helps to determine if other factors have influenced its successful completion. Effectiveness can be linked to the mobilization of the right resources and partners, and to the right choice of target group or HIBs.

Figure 12. Key points of the impact assessment focusing on changes in eating habits (Planchat from Dufour, Breyne, 2011)

A wide variety of tools and approaches for evaluation (e.g. participatory methods, beneficiary surveys, etc.) exists. But the choice of methods and tools will depend on: Program/ intervention behaviours strategy, the quality of the tools plan to be used to satisfy the evaluation objectives, available resources to implement the best and efficient tools, feasibility of indicators (themes and time).

3.1.2. Who is planning the impact?

We consider participative research to be an interesting tool for implementing participatory approach to the co-creation of one or more interventions, recommendations and decisions. The primary objective of a participatory research is to facilitate stakeholder expression and debate, in the aim to build knowledge, action and, if possible, recommendations (Barret, 2003) (in line with the learning loops in Annex L, and from tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge, promoting social and open innovation).

Indeed, in this living lab context, the researcher aims to contribute to a science of action⁴ (Lardon, 2011) to support changes in eating behaviour. The research not only produces and disseminates scientific knowledge on the need to change behavior but also produces knowledge for the actions to accompany these changes, which themselves contribute to implementing these changes. The researcher cannot do this alone but with the policymakers, food system stakeholders and the citizen because its legitimacy rests on its contribution to collective reflection and to getting people moving: these conceptual and methodological contributions enable us to make the most of the knowledge and behaviour of the people involved, and to combine them in the search for innovative solutions adapted to the theories of change. These arguments lead us to propose a “research-intervention” approach (Hatchuel, 2000, in Lardon, 2011; The BehaviourWorks Method Book, 2021) to impact planning and the tools needed to achieve it.

This posture requires researchers to have a triple skill set:

1. as referential designers,
2. as processors via tools to bring different modes of reasoning to bear on behavior change,
3. and as mediators to facilitate the translation of the needs of citizens and stakeholders by setting up places for dialogue, such as workshops.

Policymakers can help researchers by finding the human and financial resources to do the following tasks (Barthe, Trognon, 2011):

1. Analysis and diagnosis of the local food system: to analyze territorial dynamics and diagnose the needs and potential of a territory’s food system and food environments (Turner et al., 2018)
2. Program monitoring: to plan, organize, and manage complex food projects involving multiple stakeholders.
3. Communication: to communicate effectively with various food system actors, including local authorities, citizens, and private partners.
4. Consultation and mediation: to facilitate participatory processes and manage conflicts between different territorial actors.
5. Innovation and adaptation: Introduce and test new practices, share solutions for adapting to changes at different scales and with different policies already in place.

Within this model linked with the living lab and CWG, researchers and policy makers can not only gain a solid understanding of the policy context and issues on the ground, but also develop an understanding of the organizational context and where and how to integrate research practices and evidence to strengthen policy and decision-making processes and outcomes.

Ongoing long-term relationships between policymakers, researchers, consumers and local food system stakeholders enable intractable problems and recurring challenges to be tackled in a much more iterative and exploratory way.

3.1.3. How and when to plan the impact

Nutritional interventions are aimed at changing people's eating habits towards healthier behaviors. However, evaluations of those interventions still find dissatisfaction with their impact and effectiveness in target

⁴ According to Sylvie Lardon (2011), the sciences of action focus on all the concepts, methods, tools and devices made available to policymakers and stakeholders to support the design, implementation and evaluation of their programs. This includes an interdisciplinary scientific approach aimed at understanding and improving policy development practices in given territories. It integrates aspects such as adapting to the different scales of public action and the shared vision of the program.

populations (Abou Jaoudé, 2019). This measure may vary depending on the type of project and the strategic objectives that the policymakers wish to achieve.

According to the FAO (Dufour, Breyne, 2011), it is impossible to prove with certainty that the changes observed in all populations benefiting from the intervention are due to the intervention itself (due to the difficulty of parameterizing all the influencing factors and the consumer's food environment). But a living lab scale limits this bias: impact assessment validated scientifically and, because of the participative research with stakeholders, enables a better understanding of the intervention's impact on the target population.

It is essential to design impact measurement at the program conception stage (Dufour, Breyne, 2011). Indeed, sharing the program logic with policymakers and stakeholders provides the essential elements for success measure and clarifies what needs to be evaluated: nature and magnitude of changes, “paths” to achieve the desired impact, choice of methods to be used at the time of program design according to objectives, budget, human resources, etc.

3.1.4. Practical and ethical constraints of interventions in participative research

Whatever the interventions, it is essential to adapt impact measures to the specific context of the intervention and to the practical and ethical constraints of the research (The BehaviourWorks Method Book, 2021).

- Practical constraints:
 - Alignment with intervention and trial objectives
 - Feasibility within design and resource constraints
 - Validity and reliability of measurements, particularly important for scientific publication
 - Ability to exploit existing data
 - Comparability with external standards or data
 - Assessment of the representativeness of the sample
 - Inclusion of relevant control variables, moderators and mediators
 - Interdisciplinary coherence of the theories and methods used
 - Ethical constraints:
 - Inclusive participation of all legitimate stakeholders
 - Risks of identification of participants
 - Informed consent, particularly for observational methods
 - The burden imposed on participants
 - Potential risks of psychological harm
- ### 3.2. Define measures of success
- Legal and reputational implications for participants and organizations involved

Addressing the measurement of success is partly based on the following question: *why and how can we know whether our intervention has worked on the one hand, and has a real impact on changing the behaviour of target populations on the other?*

Effective evaluation of behavior changes programs, particularly in nutrition, requires defining success measures that are adapted to the different audiences we want to adopt them with. These behavior changes can be adopted by:

- citizens / beneficiaries / end-users / consumers
- and/or stakeholders because, among other things, they can have a direct or indirect influence on consumers, and conversely, consumers can have an influence on stakeholders (e.g., choice of students in a college to eat less meat in the canteen and/or choice of a cook to offer meat less often).

For this, various challenges arise, and considerations are essential to consider in the selection and application of measures to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions aimed at dietary behavior change.

Check list of challenges and considerations (The BehaviourWorks Method Book, 2021):

- Ensure that eating behavior intervention programs are implemented through a targeted and co-constructed **strategic approach** rather than through organizational habit.
For example, in the French PLANEAT living lab with children, during the diagnosis, we observed that various food education associations operate in schools on one or two interventions, only because the educational program resulting from national policies requires it. But no strategy from the teacher, parents or associations aimed at measuring the impact of these interventions was implemented. Also, thanks to the living lab, at least several meetings with local policymakers, teachers, associations, parents and researchers were implemented upstream of the interventions to co-construct a targeted strategic approach.
- Consider the **difficulties of target people in giving ownership to change their own behavior** but also in asking other stakeholders to do so. Since there is no priority given to behavioral change, there are even fewer ways to measure results in terms of preventing high-impact behaviors.
- Linking success measures to relevant decision-making within programs. Here are some examples of success measures that can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of an intervention program:
 - **Key Performance Indicators:** These are quantifiable measures that help track progress towards goals. For example, meeting numbers, meeting intervention schedules, and the quality of educational or communication deliverables about the intervention, adaptability of pre-consumer surveys (the same survey for adults and children cannot have the same communication format), etc.
 - **Roles, involvement and commitment over time of stakeholders:** measure whether certain stakeholders intervene or not in the conduct of the intervention; or they are simply consulted in the construction of the intervention; or even if have already practiced these interventions. The indicators relate, for example, to the commitment regimes of the actors (refer to Annex J), e.g. evaluation of motivations before and after via individual interviews.
 - **Stakeholder satisfaction:** Measuring the satisfaction of consumers, team members and investors can indicate the success of the intervention. Satisfaction surveys and regular feedback loops can be used
 - **Financial results:** This includes measures such as the return on investment of participants in implementing this type of intervention (e.g.: saving on the budget, quality of the restitution and time to associate the research with the intervention rather than carrying it out with only a design office).
 - **Impact on the organization and team performance:** measure how the project contributed to the organization's strategic objectives, such as improving processes or practices

For example, in the French PLAN'EAT living lab with children: the intervention focused on the creation of a working group between canteen cooks, elected officials and supply stakeholders. Following this intervention carried out over more than 10 meetings and focus groups, the cooks now collaborate and share resources, for example for the joint purchase of high-quality local products to reduce costs, discuss their human resources to develop the missions of their employees to be closer to the children and support behavioral changes. This makes it possible to monitor the team's dynamics, their collaboration and productivity strategies as an indicator of success.

- A key point of behavior change is based on **envisaging tensions between stakeholders**. To do this, two approaches can be apprehended:
 - Taking into consideration when it comes to a request to change behavior where **the general interest** (e.g.: reduction in meat consumption linked to environmental issues) **comes up against private interest** (e.g. in rural areas with only livestock farming systems, it is culturally almost impossible to adopt this behavior from the point of view of consumers). The participatory approach is based on the expression of these interests (Barret, 2003) but should not stop at this stage because the expression of particular interests does not constitute the general interest. It is important to start

from the perception that everyone has of high-impact behaviors and to contribute to the broadening of circles of awareness and their scales (micro, meso, macro) of knowledge and actors who may have a role to play in supporting these behavioral changes.

- Considering **the varied and sometimes contradictory needs** (see Annex K) of the different stakeholders and beneficiaries contributes **to the definition of** behavior change success.

In conclusion of this chapter, the judicious selection of success measures is crucial to assess the real effectiveness of behavior change programs and to guide decision-making. This complex task requires a thorough understanding of the program objectives, the intervention context, and the targeted change mechanisms.

This chapter presents the importance of rigorously evaluating the effectiveness of behavioural interventions, as well as the main evaluation approaches and considerations for choosing the most appropriate methodology. Trial interventions are procedures or treatments administered to participants as part of a clinical trial. These interventions are designed to evaluate their impact on health outcomes. In participative research approach, one way to protect your evaluation from validity threats is to use a comparison or control group of individuals who do not participate in the program to compare to individuals who do participate in the program.

3.3. The Interventions

3.3.1. Observational and experimental designs

Evaluation design is the structure or framework chosen to carry out the evaluation. There are two main models of evaluation: observational and experimental (Food Safety Education – FDA 2023⁵).

- **An observational study** is a study design in which participants are not pre-assigned to participate in the program or not (control/comparison group).
- **An experimental study** involves an intentional assignment of participants to the experimental/intervention group and the control/comparison group. This allows the evaluator to alter the independent variable (the program or activity) and be able to control external factors that influence the outcome variable. Experimental designs are not always easy to implement, but are the best option for reducing internal threats to validity

Three common evaluations with experimental study approaches can be performed (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021):

1. The randomized controlled trial (RCT)

- Considered the gold standard for establishing causal relationships
- Involves random assignment of participants to intervention and control groups
- Allows observed differences to be attributed to the intervention

Below are some useful toolboxes and checklists specifically for conducting and evaluating RCTs in food behaviours. These resources can help ensure that your RCTs in food behaviours are well-designed, methodologically sound, and accurately reported.

- CASP Randomised Controlled Trial Checklist: This checklist helps to critically appraise RCTs by guiding through key questions about the study design, methodology, results, and applicability. It is a great tool for ensuring the quality and reliability of RCTs in food behaviour research ([CASP-checklist-randomised-controlled-trials-RCT-2024.pdf](#))
- JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Randomized Controlled Trials: This tool provides a comprehensive checklist to assess the methodological quality of RCTs, focusing on aspects like randomization, blinding, and outcome measurement: [EMT Report](#)

⁵ [Planning and Evaluation 101 - a Toolkit for Consumer Food Safety Educators](#)

2. Pre-post design with control group:

- Quasi-experimental approach without randomization
- Compares pre/post outcome trends between an intervention group and a similar control group
- Allows control of general trends independent of the intervention
- Example: [Planning and Evaluation 101 - a Toolkit for Consumer Food Safety Educators](#)

3. Pre-post design without control group:

- Compares pre- and post-intervention results for a single group (Figure 13)
- Useful when a control group is not possible
- Limits causal attribution of observed effects

Evaluation Design	Description/Example	Benefits	Limitations
One group, retrospective pre/post-test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect both pre- and post-test data after implementing the program. The pre-test will involve participants thinking back to their experience before the program. • Example: You implement a food safety workshop and then hand out a two-part (pre- and post-) survey before participants leave. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good to use when you are unable to collect traditional pre-test/baseline data. • Generally inexpensive. • May be the only design option if you do not plan ahead and decide to evaluate once the program has already begun. • May demonstrate more accurately how much participants feel they have benefited from the program 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Without a comparison group, this design is not very useful in understanding whether a change in the outcome variable is actually due to the program. • Examples of potential validity threats: Recall bias and social desirability. Social desirability can be more influential in a retrospective pre-test than a traditional pre-test

Figure 33. Evaluation Designs – Description, Benefits, and Limitations for pre-post design without control group – FDA, 2023)

The choice of approach depends on several criteria:

- The evaluation question: Is the objective to establish causality or simply to observe changes?
- Budget and available resources: An RCT is not necessarily more expensive if the measures are simple.
- Practical feasibility: Is randomization possible? Are there risks of contamination between groups?
- Potential sample size: Some approaches require fewer participants.
- Ethical considerations: Is it acceptable to deprive some participants of the intervention?
- Type of measurements used: Some approaches are better suited to repeated measurements.
- The context: Is a real-life or laboratory trial preferable?

It is recommended to (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021; FDA, 2023):

- Consult stakeholders to weight these criteria
- Consider creative options for improving the ecological validity of laboratory tests
- Strike a balance between internal validity (causal attribution) and external validity (generalization of results)
- Adapt the level of rigor to project priorities and constraints

In conclusion of this chapter, there is no such thing as a perfect evaluation design. The most appropriate approach depends on the context and specific objectives. A well-executed evaluation, even with a less rigorous design, may be more useful than a poorly executed evaluation with a theoretically optimal design. The key is to put in place a robust evaluation framework to reliably measure the real impact of behavioural interventions.

3.4.1. Hierarchy of impacts

Proposing a hierarchy of intervention impact measures highlights the need not to limit ourselves to the most easily accessible measures, but to strive to assess the real and long-term impacts of interventions. In simple terms, it is about answering the following question related to theory of change approaches: “how and why does the initiative make a difference (compared to others)” (Weiss, 1995). The “how” can take the form of

3.4.1.1. Evaluate and adapt impact

The Behaviour Works Method Book (2021) proposes a hierarchy of measures, ranging from the easiest to the most difficult to measure, but also from the least to the most important (Figure 14). Typically, the first two levels a) and b) are easily achieved. It is at levels c) and d) that there is an increasing need for expertise capabilities (whether internal or with researchers):

- Capabilities, inputs and outputs** (i.e., what quantity/quality of effort/behavioral changes are you seeing). These can be complemented by immediate results indicators (i.e., what proportion of the target audience you are reaching, who is participating, user experience, satisfaction with the event, etc.).
- Antecedents of behaviour change** (i.e. known drivers of change that, if met, are likely to lead to the adoption of a behaviour). In technical terms, ‘behavioural mechanisms and mediators’ – for example, after attending the event, did participants increase their desire to act or their confidence in their ability to do so? Did they change their needs and/or commitment regimes (see Annex J and K)?
- Primary indicators of adoption of the behavior change itself**, often measurable during or shortly after the intervention (but not always), and preferably compared to a reference or control group.
- Lagging indicators of the desired impact motivating the initiative**, often measurable later and with more confounding and contributing factors. These are the “ambient conditions” which are often closely linked to the intervention or its objectives, or even to its test conditions (Henri et al., 2021): users are only interviewed; the intervention is only tested in laboratory conditions; the intervention is implemented in realistic conditions; in simulation in the laboratory; the intervention is in real life in conditions linked to the consumers' lives.

Figure 14. Hierarchy of intervention impact measures example (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021)

3.4.2. Monitoring impact

Monitoring impact means to observe, measure, and evaluate the effects or outcomes of an intervention over time. This process helps to understand whether the intended goals are being achieved and to identify any unintended consequences. Monitoring impact typically involves:

1. **Setting Indicators:** Defining specific, measurable indicators that will be used to assess progress and impact.
2. **Collecting Data:** Gathering data through various methods such as surveys, interviews, observations, or using existing data sources.
3. **Analyzing Results:** Interpreting the collected data to determine the extent of the impact.
4. **Reporting Findings:** Communicating the results to stakeholders to inform decision-making and future actions.
5. **Adjusting Strategies:** Making necessary adjustments to improve outcomes based on the findings

Typology of indicators

Common indicators used to monitor impact can vary depending on the context and goals of the project or program. These indicators help organizations and stakeholders understand the progress and effectiveness of their initiatives, enabling them to make informed decisions and adjustments as needed. Below are some widely used indicators across different fields:

- **Input Indicators:** Measure the resources invested in an intervention, such as financial, human, material, or informational resources
- **Output Indicators:** Track the direct products or services delivered by a, such as the number of workshops conducted, reports published, or people trained
- **Outcome Indicators:** Assess the short-term and medium-term effects of a intervention, like changes in knowledge, attitudes, behaviours, or conditions among the target population
- **Impact Indicators:** Evaluate the long-term effects and overall changes resulting from a intervention, such as improvements in health, economic conditions, or environmental quality
- **Efficiency Indicators:** Measure how well resources are used to achieve outputs, often expressed as cost per unit of output
- **Effectiveness Indicators:** Assess the extent to which the project achieves its intended outcomes and impacts
- **Sustainability Indicators:** Evaluate the likelihood that the benefits of a project will continue after the project ends
- **Equity Indicators:** Measure the distribution of benefits among different groups, ensuring that vulnerable or marginalized populations are also benefiting

Source : [Selecting indicators for impact evaluation - Research to Action](#)

3.4.3. Evaluate and adapt impacts during the program

The Living Lab Markers (Henri et al., 2021) are a tool designed to evaluate and qualify these measures based on collective innovation processes. Consumer and stakeholder participation and awareness-raising is an integral part of the formulation and implementation of impact measures, including the establishment of continuous feedback mechanisms throughout the various stages of the intervention program, and the adjustment of impact measures according to the actions developed based on standards, policies and specific consumer needs (Figure 15).

The collective innovation process is a method that relies on the collaboration and participation of multiple stakeholders. According to "The Living Lab Markers", collective innovation processes are characterized by several key steps, in an iterative format, with a view to maintaining behavioral changes over the long term (defining action plans always in a living lab approach):

- **Needs exploration:** identify and understand user and stakeholder needs (see Annex K)
- **Co-creation of the solution to change behavior:** Involve users and stakeholders in the design of the solution.
- **Prototyping:** Developing solution/intervention prototypes to test ideas and concepts. Co-creation steps can be used.
- **Testing the solution through intervention:** Evaluate the intervention with users to collect feedback and improve the solutions for supporting dietary behaviour change.
- **Deployment and dissemination:** Implement the finalized solution and disseminate it to target users or to the same users but over a longer period of time.

It is important to note that this approach is not suitable for measuring the long-term societal impact of the intervention. Other post-intervention impact measurement tools are required. Rather, it is recommended to use it for an intermediate or final evaluation of an intervention and may or may not have been conceived from the outset with measurement indicators.

EIGHT MARKERS HAVE BEEN DEFINED:

- M1 FORMULATION OF THE NEED AND ITERATIVE PROCESS
- M2 ROLE OF USERS (and more generally of stakeholders)
- M3 PLURALITY OF USERS AND STAKEHOLDERS (companies, public authorities, researchers)
- M4 INVOLVEMENT OF USERS AND STAKEHOLDERS IN THE CO-CREATION AND PROTOTYPING PROCESS
- M5 TEST CONDITIONS
- M6 OUTPUTS (product, service, tool, etc.)
- M7 ACCESSIBILITY AND DISSEMINATION OF OUTPUT
- M8 ABILITY TO ACT

Figure 55. The Godin Institute and the AISBL Academy of Management to boost the e-health and gastronomy sectors in Wallonia (Henri et al., 2021)

These iterative processes involve a diversity of actors, with a central place given to the target group (users/beneficiaries). The objective is to develop solutions adapted to the real needs of users while strengthening the capacity to act of the people involved. This tool makes it possible to set up participatory projects, evaluate ongoing projects and define action plans for a living lab approach. The living lab methodology is therefore distinguished by its iterative nature, the diversity of actors involved and the centrality of users.

PLANEAT partner ICONS developed a Process Evaluation Framework outlined in the IR8, an evaluation tool partially linked with this tool and its eight evaluation markers abovementioned. We will not elaborate further on this information, apart from presenting a PLANEAT case study from the French living lab.

PLAN'EAT CASE STUDY

REDUCING MEAT CONSUMPTION IN CHILDREN, 6-10Y, LIVING LAB FRANCE

Gastronomy, when combined with educational and environmental values, can become a formidable learning tool. With this in mind, members of the French Living Lab, such as 12 municipalities in the Clermont-Ferrand Metropolis, in collaboration with elementary school cooks and their staff, the local Ferrandaise breed breeders' association and teachers, organized a major culinary event: the Ferrandais Bourguignon. This experiment, which is still ongoing (2023-2025), was designed to raise children's awareness of responsible eating, while highlighting the Ferrandaise beef industry.

The aim of this project was twofold: on the one hand, to promote quality food on children's plates, focusing on the health aspect of "eating less meat, but better" (HIB reduce red meat). On the other hand, to highlight, in an educational way, the entire food production circuit, and the obstacles and levers involved in supplying collective catering with "very" local, high-quality products. Indeed, Ferrandaise cattle help maintain the natural grasslands of our mid-mountain region, and are quite resilient in the face of climate change.

This experiment took shape with the preparation of Ferrandaise meals in 12 canteens in the Clermont-Ferrand area, for a total of 14,000 meals served. To guarantee an environmentally friendly approach and encourage direct exchanges, purchases were made directly with local farmers, often outside the traditional channels of public procurement. Nine farmers contributed by supplying an average of 60g of quality meat per child (instead of 70g).

At the same time, INRAE worked with some of the pilot schools in the PLANEAT project, to carry out satisfaction surveys on a digital tablet with 784 children on the day of the meal and one year later on a recipe for bourguignon but with more standard meat. The aim was to gain a better understanding of high-impact changes in eating behavior, such as reducing meat consumption in favor of better quality. This approach made it possible to actively involve children in the change process, raising their awareness of the health, environmental and economic issues linked to their diet.

The event was a great success, both in terms of participation and positive feedback. 72% of children were enthusiastic about the culinary experience, while canteen teams, educators and families praised the initiative (researchers did interviews with them).

Evaluation markers of this intervention are the following (indicators corresponding to Figure 15 above):

Indicator M1: formulation of needs and iterative process

- **Impact:** The need was questioned and redefined with users and certain stakeholders throughout the project.
- **Measure tools and methods:** 1 focus-group workshops to report the needs, strategies, 5 working co-groups and their recoding to co-create intervention, real life interventions, feed-back focus groups and evaluation of needs and new strategies

Indicator M2: role of users (and stakeholders more generally)

- **Impact:** Users (Children) are consulted, but stakeholders are involved in the operational and strategic management of the intervention
- **Measure tools and methods:** for children 3 main methods (canteen participative observation, micro interviews with children, digital tablets surveys during interventions), interviews with stakeholder before, just after and 1 year after the intervention.

Indicator M3: plurality of users and stakeholders (companies, public authorities, researchers)

- **Impact:** The project involves a wide range of players from different backgrounds and territories, with diverging interests.
- **Measure tools and methods:** a tracking map of the various stakeholder's involvement (refer to annex J) into the program, before, during, just after the intervention and 1 year later (process still ongoing in 2025 and 2026)

Indicator M4: involvement of users and stakeholders in the co-creation and prototyping process

- **Impact:** Stakeholders are involved in the co-creation of a functional, reproducible experiment. In October 2025 cooks will consolidating Ferrandaise meat sourcing project for the coming years and developing their expertise in other products, in particular a vegetarian menu.
- **Measure tools and methods:** same as indicator M1

Indicator M5: test conditions

- **Impact:** The prototype Bourguignon meal was tested in real-life conditions.
- **Measure tools and methods:** same as indicator M1 and M3

Indicator M6: outputs (product, service, tool, etc.) & M7: Accessibility and dissemination of output

- **Impact:** The project aims to encourage new collaborations within the community, and new uses beyond the territory of action (refer to Annex M).
- **Measure tools and methods:** the same project will be developed on a more rural area then the Metropole and with 10 news cooks and around 8000 new consumers (schools and hospitals). The shared objectives to implement intervention strategies aimed at promoting behaviour change by the living lab project and its stakeholders (coordinating researchers and stakeholders in the territory where the living lab is implemented).

Indicator M8 : ability to act

- **Impact:** The action encourages stakeholders to pass on new skills and knowledge.
- **Measure tools and methods:** tracking of all information, report, communication supports realized by the stakeholders (social media of farmers association, focus groups in classroom of children who were evaluated with digital tablet, participative observation of municipal meetings with parents, cooks and officials).

3.4.4. Evaluate long term impact of the program

For this chapter, we propose to cross-reference three studies that offer us a complementary perspective on the assessment of eating behaviours and the factors that influence them over time. The study by Recours and Hebel (2007) highlights the importance of generational effects in the evolution of eating habits in France. It shows how eating habits evolve over time, with a transition towards increased consumption of processed products and a reduction in the time devoted to meals, particularly among younger generations.

The USAID Advancing Nutrition (2021) report brings a more global and applied perspective, focusing on strategies for monitoring and promoting behaviour change in the field of nutrition. It highlights the importance of a multi-sectoral approach and the need to adapt interventions to specific cultural contexts.

INRAE's collective expertise (INRAE, 2010) offers a detailed analysis of the multiple determinants of dietary behaviour, ranging from biological factors to socio-economic influences. It also provides an overview of changes in eating habits in France and suggests courses of action for assessing improvements in eating habits.

Figure 66. C. Planchat from Recours & Hebel, 2007; USAID Advancing Nutrition, 2021; INRAE, 2010

These studies highlight the need for a holistic, long-term approach to understanding and influencing dietary behavior. They underline the importance of taking generational, cultural and socio-economic differences into account when developing policies and interventions to promote healthy, sustainable eating.

Here is a summary of some indicators and their sub-indicators presented in Figure 16:

- **Longitudinal approach:**
 - Establish long-term cohort studies to monitor changes in dietary behaviors over time.
 - Use mixed methods combining quantitative (consumer surveys) and qualitative (interviews, observations) data to obtain a more complete view of changes.
- **Multi-level indicators:**
 - Develop indicators to consider the different determinants (biological, psychological, socio-cultural, economic).
 - Integrate measures at different scales: individual, family, community and societal.
- **Intergenerational analysis:**
 - Integrate an analysis of generation effects into monitoring behavioral changes (e.g. according to Recours and Hebel (2007), generations born before 1937 have more traditional eating habits, with higher consumption of bread, potatoes and fresh vegetables, while generations born after 1967 consume more processed products, ready-made meals and sugary drinks.
 - Compare trajectories of behaviour changes across different age cohorts.

Below are additional indicators linked with public policies impacts:

- **Health impacts:**
 - Monitor the evolution of health indicators related to diet (obesity rates, prevalence of chronic diseases, etc.).
 - Use biomarkers to assess the nutritional impact of dietary changes.
- **Environmental impacts:**
 - Integrate environmental impact measures (greenhouse gas emissions, resource use) linked to food choices, as suggested in the INRAE report.
- **Socio-economic impacts:**
 - Assess the consequences of behavioral changes on the local economy, food production systems and employment in the agri-food sector.
- **Well-being and quality of life:**
 - Include measures of satisfaction, well-being and quality of life related to eating practices.

3.4.5. Boundaries of evaluation

Several limitations in the evaluation of behavior change programs should also be considered (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021):

- The lack of skills required by creators, organizers, facilitators and evaluators of the intervention. Care must be taken to consider individual skills and shared skills due to the living lab and the intervention research objective.
- Excessive focus on immediate results to the detriment of long-term change mechanisms
- The difficulty of including measures of behavioral mechanisms or mediators without compromising trial fidelity
- Time and resource constraints limit measurement of long-term impacts

- The tension between the need to demonstrate short-term effectiveness and the pursuit of long-term goals

We advocate here for a more systemic approach to evaluation, characterized by:

- A priority given to loop learning (refer to Annex L.), to capacity building and to the adaptability of both individual actors, of the ecosystem in which they operate and of their territories and social norms.
- The importance of clearly explaining the underlying behavior change theory
- Integrating behavioral aspects into broader, adaptive theories of change

It is also important to adopt a participatory approach considering both short-term accountabilities and needs, and long-term behaviour change objectives. We encourage constant monitoring of how policymakers can better align their success indicators with their social innovation objectives, while preserving scientific rigor and ethical integrity in their intervention and evaluation methods.

3.5. Scale and share findings This chapter discusses three key strategies developed for maximizing the impact of effective behavioral interventions: scaling, dissemination, and knowledge transfer/brokering (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021). These three strategies – scaling, diffusion, knowledge transfer – are complementary to maximize the impact of behavioral interventions:

- Scaling up helps extend the reach of an effective intervention
- Dissemination makes the results known to relevant decision-makers
- Knowledge transfer integrates these results into policies and practices

3.5.1. Scaling

The intervention strategies in this toolbox are tailored to the specific target groups represented by the PLANEAT living labs. However, it is important to distinguish between a strategy linked to a research intervention and a scaling-up strategy linked to the implementation of a public policy. According to The Behaviour Works Method Book (2021), the results of research and specific interventions can often be considered sufficient to have a concrete impact in the real world. Decision-makers may think that the adoption of scientific findings can be enough to justify their policy. However, it can take more than 10-20 years to see the effectiveness of the transition from an intervention tested on a sample to a public policy applicable to the whole population. This is partly due to the quality of the dissemination of the intervention, in terms of the uses and habits of organizations, the extension of its geographical scope and its adaptation to territorial complexities (see Annex M). Most of the time, scaling up involves applying an effective intervention to change the behavior of a larger number of people. But a variety of scaling objectives can be considered. They are closely linked to the expectations and strategies of decision-makers. Thus, scaling up can be aimed at (Figure 17):

- Increasing the scope of the intervention (renewal / development):**
 - on a wider population, i.e., increasing the number of people reached
 - on the number of institutions or changing their practices
 - on a broader range of public policies, or influencing the creation of new policies
- Adapting the intervention :**
 - to a new audience (e.g., created for men, then adapted for women)

- to integrate new values, cultures, beliefs, economies... (e.g.: adapted to urban populations, then adapted to rural populations).

Complementing the intervention to develop new behaviors

- e.g.: the intervention is designed to reduce consumption of refined sugary breakfast cereals, it can be complemented by industrial fruity breakfast beverages.

Figure 77. C. Planchat adapted from *The Behaviour Works Method Book*, 2021

It is important to consider the challenges of scaling:

- Lack of external validity: Interventions may not work outside their initial testing context.
- Loss of fidelity when deploying at scale.
- Reduced profitability or efficiency when adapting for widespread implementation.
- Difficulty in mobilizing and maintaining commitment and resources at scale.

To improve scaling, it is recommended to:

- Consider scaling from the selection of target behavior and design of the intervention.
- Obtain commitment from partner organizations as early as possible.
- Use scalability assessment tools, such as the Scale-Up Toolkit⁶ (Milat et al., 2020). The Scale-Up Toolkit helps policymakers and practitioners assess the suitability of health interventions for broader implementation by evaluating factors like context, effectiveness, and sustainability. It provides a structured approach to determine whether an intervention is ready for scale-up, needs more information, or is not suitable yet.

⁶ Intervention Scalability Assessment Tool: A decision support tool for health policy makers and implementers | Health Research Policy and Systems

Relevant scaling factors (acronym SCALE):

SCALE is an acronym used to evaluate the suitability of health interventions for scaling up. It refers to the process of increasing the size, scope, or impact of an intervention, project, or operation. This often involves expanding from a smaller, controlled setting to a larger, more widespread implementation, ensuring that the intervention remains effective and sustainable on a larger scale. Applying the SCALE factors according to The Behaviour Works Method Book (2021) involves:

- **Simple:** Design interventions that are easy to understand and implement without needing specialized skills or equipment. This ensures that the procedure can be widely adopted with minimal training.
- **Consistent:** The intervention is tested in contexts similar to large-scale deployment. Conduct trials in environments that closely resemble the larger context where the intervention will be deployed. This helps verify that the intervention will perform reliably in real-world settings.
- **Adaptable:** Clearly define the behavior change mechanisms and allow for flexibility to adjust the intervention based on different contexts or populations. This adaptability ensures the intervention remains effective across various settings.
- **Likeable:** The intervention is appreciated by organizations and the target audience. Engage with stakeholders, including organizations and the target audience, to gather feedback and ensure the intervention is well-received and meets their needs. Positive reception is crucial for successful implementation.
- **Effective:** the intervention is perceived as effective and cost-effective. Demonstrate through evidence that the intervention achieves its intended outcomes and is cost-effective. This involves rigorous testing and evaluation to build confidence in its effectiveness and economic viability

3.5.2. The broadcast

Dissemination aims to make research findings known to decision makers and stakeholders. It involves developing strategies, planning and writing content about the research, and then communicating these findings to key audiences.

Key components of diffusion:

- **Source:** the recognized sender of the message (credibility, reliability)
- **Message:** the information broadcast (length, complexity)
- **Channel:** the means of diffusion (modality, scope)
- **Audience:** the recipients of the message (engagement, knowledge)

To plan and execute an effective broadcast, the **SPREADS** checklist is suggested (The Behaviour Works Method Book, 2021):

- **Strategy:** Define objectives, target audience and key messages
- **Preparation:** Plan activities and schedule
- **Resources:** Identify resource needs and budget
- **Engagement:** Engage stakeholders and collaborators
- **Adaptation:** Adapt messages to different audiences
- **Dissemination:** Communicate through various channels, **S - Monitoring:** Evaluate impact and adjust strategy

3.5.3. Knowledge transfer and brokerage

Knowledge transfer and brokering aims to systematically integrate knowledge into policy and program development. It involves translating information into accessible forms and making deliberate efforts to integrate it into decision-making.

Key objectives of knowledge transfer:

- Share what is known (results, best practices)
- Identify the remaining unknowns
- Criticize current and proposed policies and practices
- Providing new ideas

Knowledge brokering includes:

- Relationship development
- Ongoing communication and support
- Personalized strategies to build capacity

Knowledge brokers act as a bridge between researchers and practitioners. They can be researchers embedded in a partner organization or experts internal to the organization.

To improve knowledge transfer and brokerage:

- Establish long-term partnerships between researchers and organizations
- Adopt a “researcher-in-residence” model for ongoing advice
- Develop a mutual understanding of the context and issues
- Train internal champions and experts
- Build capacity through training and learning by doing

Conclusion of chapter 3 – Planning the impact

In summary, chapter 3 highlights the importance of considering implementation and impact from the design stage of a behavioral intervention. Researchers and policymakers are encouraged to actively plan for scaling up, dissemination, and knowledge transfer to maximize the societal benefits of effective behavioral science-based interventions.

Conclusions and next steps

The PLAN'EAT toolbox for behaviour change intervention strategies is a resource for driving healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours at the micro (consumer) level. It leverages a scientifically rigorous, multi-actor approach that integrates evidence-based research, participatory methods, and tailored interventions. By focusing on individual consumers while acknowledging systemic influences, the toolbox provides policymakers and researchers with actionable strategies for achieving impactful dietary behaviour changes.

The document underscores the importance of addressing barriers and leveraging opportunities at multiple levels. It employs frameworks like the Behaviour Change Wheel (BCW) and COM-B model to systematically identify leverage points and design effective interventions. These tools are adaptable to diverse contexts, including the nine living labs of PLAN'EAT, each representing unique demographic and environmental conditions.

The toolbox should not just be a theoretical guide but a practical instrument for fostering healthier, sustainable eating behaviours. It encourages collaboration among stakeholders, emphasizes the role of education, and offers tools for rigorous evaluation and scalability. It aims to help address public health and environmental challenges by influencing dietary choices across Europe.

An important aspect not covered in this toolbox, since it is outside its scope, is the political strategy for adoption and implementation. Policy changes related to diets will inevitably encounter resistance from various stakeholders, making it crucial to address this opposition to achieve meaningful change. Although this dimension is beyond the scope of this toolbox, it is essential for those promoting the toolbox to decision-makers to take it into account.

As the next step, the toolbox will support PLAN'EAT tasks 4.3.2 and 4.3.3 in designing behavioural change interventions for each living lab target group, covering also clinical studies.

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